

SATISFACTORY

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
BR	Border Router
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
LAN	Local Area Network
MR	Multi-Radio
MRGW	Multi-Radio Gateway
MRNs	Multi-Radio Nodes
PBL	Points, badges and leaderboards
REST	Representational State Transfer
SM	Spectrum Manager
SNs	Sensor Nodes
SR	Single-Radio
SRGW	SR gateway
SSN	Spectrum Sensing Node
SSN	Spectrum Sensing Node
UI	User Interface
WCM	World Class Manufacturing Program

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (H2020), reporting the results of the activities carried out by WP2. SatisFactory aims to develop an ecosystem of innovative technological components that would assist the daily operations of the people working at industrial environment. More specifically, the developments of SatisFactory will be demonstrated to three diverse shop floors from discrete manufacturing (COMAU), batch products manufacturing (SUNLIGHT Systems) and continuous processes (CERTH/CPERI).

Deliverable D2.3 is compiled with a collaborative effort of three partners, namely FIT, ISMB and CERTH. It documents the concepts and the iterative process of ideation of as to how these concepts were generated and how, with the lapse of time and analysis, they evolved. D2.3 explains in detail various iterations of the entire ideation process, starting from a set of semi-structured user interviews with the workers in the pilot factories and resulting in actual working prototypes. The details of the interfaces and implementation details are discussed in D3.2 and D3.4 respectively.

Furthermore, this deliverable D2.3 discusses the iterative process of the concept development for Suggestions Platform (FIT), the Social Interaction Platform (CERTH), Product's Future (FIT), Battery Assembly Practice Support (FIT), Protect Your Health (FIT), the Digital Andon System (ISMB) and last but not the least, the Gamification Framework (FIT). D2.3 documents the details of each use case and how these use cases are mapped to various business scenarios. In addition to that, it also explains how these use cases were designed and how this design evolved to fulfill the gathered requirements.

1 INTRODUCTION

Task T2.3 elaborates fundamental concepts and designs for the enhancement of the working environments based on the results of the domain analysis and formulated requirements in WP1. The concepts focus on increasing the attractiveness of the working environments and on improving working conditions.

The concepts were worked out in an iterative ideation process, using user-centered and value-oriented design techniques, which orientate on the gathered requirements.

As predefinition, T2.3 aims at two solution focuses. On the one hand, there is the creation of a social interaction platform. This aims at knowledge sharing and supporting the interaction between employees. On the other hand, gamification techniques shall be introduced in order to stimulate collaboration and motivate workers for doing unpopular tasks better or more often. At the same time, these techniques promise to raise the general attractiveness of the workplace.

Furthermore, T2.3 has some connections to other gamification concepts. The digital andon system is used as one visualization system for the gamification framework. It is also a part of the Gesture and Content Recognition Manager, described in D3.3 - Context-aware incident detection engine. The wireless connection for real-time services in hostile environment is mainly described in D4.1 - Development of intelligent IoT-infrastructure for the smart-sensor network.

Of course, it would be counterproductive to restrict oneself to solutions already before the concept creation process. So, gamification and social collaboration were not seen as the only possible concept outcomes. The goal was to find all solutions which are good to meet the gathered user requirements.

Summarized, this deliverable reports on concepts and on the iterative approach how to reach these concepts. Details about design or implementation of the finally selected concepts are described in other deliverables, mainly D3.2 - Situated and attractive information exchange techniques for workers and D3.4 - Collaborative platform for work process support.

2 APPROACH

This chapter introduces the methodologies and topics of this deliverable. It presents the ideation process, which was used to generate many different ideas how the attractiveness of factories can be increased for workers. This was closely related to the gathered requirements recapitulated in Chapter 3. Furthermore, background about gamification and collaboration support is given.

2.1 IDEATION

The main purpose of this task was to generate ideas as to how technologies can increase attractiveness of the involved factories in the project, having generalizability in mind so that the developed ideas are relevant for many factories outside the project as well. The project wanted to arise these ideas from the actual needs of the workers instead of presenting solutions, which were developed in management offices and are neglecting the actual real needs.

This is the rationale for the used ideation process. It started with a set of semi-structured user interviews with the workers in the pilot factories. These aimed at understanding the problems and needs of the workers. The interviews were documented and later on, the main statements, problems and solution approaches were extracted and put on paper. This extracted information allowed us to identify different problem areas and needs. The different statements were clustered and assigned to these problems and needs (cf. Figure 1).

Figure 1: Clustered statements, gathered from worker interviews

As next step, we tried to generate ideas for each of the extracted statements. For this, we tried to focus on solutions which touched social experience and gamification techniques but did not restrict ourselves to these kind of technologies. The ideas were further elaborated into concepts.

As preparation to the next iteration, the concepts were analyzed regarding different aspects. Firstly, they were linked to identified user needs and satisfactory categories as indicators to check their practical relevance (cf. Figure 2). Next, for each concept, we tried to identify the goal aimed to be achieved. If we would have had problems with defining a goal for a particular concept, this would have been an indicator that the concept is useless. Then, we checked to which Satisfactory use case and business scenario the concepts would fit in order to align with the overall Satisfactory progress. Next, we checked to which aspects of T2.3 the concepts fitted. Concepts which covered more T2.3 aspects were favored. The same is true for generalizability of the concepts. Lastly, we checked for known constraints, limitations and technical feasibility.

Based on these analyses the concepts underwent several iterations in which they were refined, rated, accepted or rejected and reassessed. This was done in partner internal discussions as well as consortium wide discussions. Furthermore, for the promising concepts first design probes were done and further user workshops were conducted.

For the resulting ideas, we went more into detail. For this, we further specified use cases and higher fidelity prototypes. This has to be seen as further iteration of the chosen concepts. Finally, we dropped some more concepts and chose to finally implement four concepts for Satisfactory: The

Suggestions for Improvement Platform, the Social Interaction Platform, the Protect your Health prototype and the Gamification Framework.

Figure 2: Concepts associated to user needs and satisfaction categories

2.2 GAMIFICATION TECHNIQUES

Gamification is described as the use of game design elements in non-game contexts (Deteding et al., 2011). Gamification is being used in different fields such as business, management, marketing and education (Dicheva et al., 2015) with the aim to increase users' motivation and engagement. Gamification mechanics may include point system, levels, leaderboards, avatars, progress bars, virtual goods/currency, badges/achievements (Gåslund, M., 2011, Dicheva et al., 2015) that can be used as need be (Gåslund, M., 2011). An example of badges and levels usage is Stackoverflow, which includes a voting system in order to increase users' participation and engagement (Dicheva et al., 2015). Users receive votes for their questions and answers increasing their reputation and earning badges.

In order to hook the users' interest at the beginning of their gamification experience at the initial stages the awards should have less prerequisites to be earned and as the game experience grows the user should feel challenged enough to continue participation. This can be achieved with fewer points needed at the beginning in order to attain the next level. While the level is being updated more points should be required to be gathered to the next level of the current skill.

(Sweetser P., Wyeth P., 2005). Although this approach is more suitable for games, findings have shown that this practice is equally efficient in gamification approach raising the level of users' engagement (Meister, 2013). At the beginning of the users' experience a tutorial regarding the use of the platform could enhance the motivation with the appropriate awards embedded in the welcome process (Meister, 2013, Sweetser P., Wyeth P., 2005).

Retaining the users' interest should be of major priority, while the gamification elements are not effective on their own, but should be used appropriately. The balance between user skills and task challenge in a game may impact the game success, considering that boredom and stress should be avoided (Sweetser P., Wyeth P., 2005). Having this in mind and the fact that the platform should be usable for different kinds of industries, the task design should be available from the factories that use the platform in order to ensure that the needs of each factory are covered. Thus, employees should be able to define tasks related to real-life and inner-platform activities through a flexible platform which provides the gamification elements. The employees should be supported when defining games' features by information regarding inclinations, interests, preferences, actions and participation of the employees in order to design tasks accordingly. This information can be aroused by the appropriate analytics that the manager may have in his/her disposal for use (Meister, 2013).

"Social gamification" combines gamification with social network elements enhancing the potential of both means. Gamification can increase users' motivation and engagement and a social network can enhance communication and collaboration between users (de-Marcos, 2016). Gamification combined with social collaboration can support social learning and at the same time can increase workers' engagement (Deloitte digital, 2012). These can be achieved through a social network-like platform where the participants can interact with each other through exchange of ideas and knowledge, grow their network and view theirs and others users' profiles and achievements (Meister, 2013). Gamification elements can also be used for recruiting new members through rewarding games that motivate peoples' participation and preparation for a work. An example is the game "My Marriot Hotel" from the homonymous hotels organization which refers to hotel management. Users manage a digital hotel which leads to participants' practicing in hotel management skills having fun and being motivated to be a part of the organization. Social interaction is also part of the recruitment managing of the organization considering that strong connections should be formed among current and future employees (Paul Slezak, 2013).

Gamification as a concept means to apply various concepts of game playing such as keeping points, achieving badges and leader boards etc. into a non-gaming environment e.g. in a factory to encourage engagement with the system in use and to motivate the workers in doing their daily routine tasks in a better way.

The concept of Gamification transforms the business models by creating new ways to extend relationships, craft longer-term engagement, and drive user loyalty. It works because it influences the motivations and desires that exist in all of us for community, feedback, achievement and reward [5].

Gartner [4] predicts that by 2015, more than 70% of Global 2000 organizations will have at least one gamified application. There are various success stories of gamification in front of us. For example, badgeville [3] is an award winning enterprise gamification and analytics solution. Figure 3 shows the screen how an employee can track his progress and achievements.

Figure 3 : Badgeville user profile

Table 1 contains various gamification mechanisms and how they are applied in various aspects of the gamification framework. Each mechanism along with its description explains how it acts as a motivator for the users.

Table 1: Overview of gamification mechanisms

Mechanism	Description	Motivator	Application
Fast Feedback	I get immediate feedback or response to actions	Mastery Progress	Upon performing a certain task, the worker will be able to view his updated points immediately via the digital screen and mobile app.
Transparency	I can see where everyone (including me) stands, quickly and easily	Progress Social Interaction	The worker will be able to view his individual points via the mobile app. The cumulative team points can be viewed via the digital screen.
Goals	I have short and long term goals to achieve	Purpose Progress Social Interaction	Every game created using the gamification framework has a “Maximum Score that can be achieved” attribute attached to it. It may vary for each game. Individually, it is one of the goals of the worker to reach this score. Regarding team effort, the workers have the goal to beat their yesterday’s score.
Badges	I can display evidence of my accomplishments	Mastery Purpose Progress Social	-Avatar Evolution -Points being translated into intangible achievements e.g. Time off

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Mechanism	Description	Motivator	Application
		Interaction	
Levelling Up	I can achieve status within my community	Mastery Purpose Progress Social Interaction	-Each game has different levels. Upon completing a certain level, the worker is moved up to the next level -Avatar Evolution
On boarding	I can learn in an engaging and compelling way	Mastery	Depends on the external system
Competition	I can see how am I doing against others	Mastery Social Interaction	The concept of competition is applied by implementing a winning streak via the digital screen. The workers compete with their own score that they accomplished the day before.
Collaboration	I can work with others to accomplish goals	Purpose Social Interaction	Team games
Community	I can see what the community is doing; the community can see me	Social Interaction	The sense of community is maintained by maintaining a single instance of gamification for all the external systems. So everyone contributes to the same collective score of all the workers of the factory by performing any task related to any of the external systems linked with the gamification framework.
Points	I can see tangible, measureable evidence of my accomplishment	Progress Social	Points are awarded upon performing tasks of different games created by the external systems. The worker will be able to view his individual points. The cumulative team points can be viewed via the digital screen.

2.3 SUPPORTING COLLABORATION PROCESSES

One of the main goals of satisfactory program is to improve attractiveness and productivity through collaboration, social interaction and gamification approaches. This chapter refers to the **Social Collaboration Platform** where users are able to exchange knowledge/experience/practices on work issues (D1.1). Additionally, the social collaboration platform is gamified itself increasing motivation of employees during work.

A preliminary research was conducted based on stakeholders' and workers' interviews and research findings on collaboration and gamification on industry field, having in mind that different kinds of factories could benefit from the use of the platform (D1.1). Based on these findings a further analysis conducted in order to ensure that the appropriate **social and collaboration elements** will be chosen

to be aligned with the needs of the users. Finally, specifications on the platform were formed regarding its tools that can support users' satisfaction and the collaboration and gamification elements that can enhance their engagement. This human-centered approach could not be beneficial without appropriate feedback on every stage of development. (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Human Centered Analysis

In previous research conducted user needs were elicited and described for each of the participant factories. The Actors were also identified, described and correlated with the Business Scenarios and User Cases defined (D1.1, D1.2). After a generic description of Use Cases (D1.2), a more specific description is attempted in this chapter in order to clarify the functionalities of the **collaboration platform in accordance to the users' needs and social gamification requirements.**

Research findings regarding the requirements that the collaboration platform should fulfill are completing the users' requirements for each Use Case presented. The result is forming at the end the specifications that the platform will have. Subsequently, functionalities of the collaboration platform are presented in accordance with the requirements. (Figure 5)

Figure 5: User Needs to Specifications

Social platform aims to increase engagement and motivation of the employees in factories through two main powerful tools that are combined in order to meet the stakeholders’ needs. Social media features combined with gamification elements could form an overall experience that enhances employees’ skills and positive feelings in the work environment. Every individual could be motivated to be engaged at work socially, cognitively and emotionally while practicing skills that provoke individual progress and positive self-feelings. As an extension, the collaboration among employees should be allowed, supported and reinforced in order to enhance team and organization progress towards satisfaction and productivity increase.

2.3.1 Collaboration Processes

Collaboration tools aim to support specific Use Cases that have been described in D1.2 in accordance to the Business Scenarios. In the same deliverable, it has been also conducted the correlation between Business Scenarios and group requirements (D1.2) (Table 2, Figure 6). According to the social collaboration requirements, the following sections present the way in which the social collaboration platform supports each Use Case that has been raised from the users’ needs.

Table 2 Use Cases referring to collaborative tools (D1.2).

Use Case	Use Case Description	Sub - Use Case	Sub- Use Case Description	Actors involved	Business Scenarios
UC-2	Learning environment with interactive training activities for multipurpose operations	2.1	In-factory training and support of workers using a flexible learning platform	Supervisors, Operators & Technicians	BSC1.1, BSC1.2, BSC2.1, BSC4.1, BSC4.3
UC-4	Intelligent decision support and maintenance for increased flexibility	4.2	Acquire work schedule and sequence of actions	Supervisors, Operators & Technicians	BSC1.1, BSC1.2, BSC2.1, BSC3.1,

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					BSC4.1, BSC4.2, BSC4.3, BSC5.1, BSC5.2, BSC5.3
UC-5	Collaboration and Social interaction for increased workers' engagement	5.1	Gamification Framework	Supervisors, Operators & Technicians	BSC1.1, BSC1.2, BSC2.1, BSC3.1, BSC4.1, BSC4.2, BSC4.3, BSC5.1, BSC5.2, BSC5.3
UC-5	Collaboration and Social interaction for increased workers' engagement	5.3	Gamified platform for suggestions for improvement	Supervisors, Operators & Technicians	BSC1.1, BSC1.2, BSC3.1
UC-5	Collaboration and Social interaction for increased workers' engagement	5.4	Instantiation of gamification framework	Supervisors, Operators & Technicians	BSC4.3, BSC5.3
UC-6	Presentation of activities and bidirectional communication for enhanced shop floor feedback	6.3	Knowledge sharing among workers based on advanced reasoning	Supervisors, Operators & Technicians	BSC1.1, BSC1.2, BSC2.1, BSC3.1, BSC4.1, BSC4.2, BSC4.3, BSC5.1, BSC5.2, BSC5.3

Figure 6: Use Case Diagram referring to Collaborative Tools

2.3.1.1 UC-2.1 In-factory training and support of workers using a flexible learning platform

A learning environment (Training and Educational Platform) for the involved actors (supervisors, operators & technicians) is needed in order to that will increase their knowledge as well as their skills for the execution of specific procedures (D1.2). Users will execute training actions while they need to be supported by their co-workers during the process in order to minimize mistakes. Through the use of a **communication tool** users would have the possibility to interact with co-workers in order to take guidelines and discuss possible problems in order to avoid malfunctions during training. Additionally, a **Questions & Answers tool** should be available for the users to increase their knowledge and enhance their skills. (Figure 7) This platform should additionally encourage the employees to use other training tools available on AR devices when they are available.

Workers use the social collaboration platform in order to

- Interact with co-workers
- Share knowledge/experience
- Ask for knowledge/experience

- Increase knowledge
- Continuously access to knowledge/best practices
- Continuously reform a documentation according to the needs
- Exchange of practices between departments/units
- Means of expressing different opinions for best practices
- Remember to practice skills/learn procedures using other tools

A learning environment could support workers on training and other issues through:

- Communication tool
- Questions & Answers tool

Figure 7: Social Collaboration Platform

- Communication tool

Interaction with co-workers could be supported through a social network-like platform where the users can connect with each other in order to communicate. **Posting** is an effective way of asking for help when trying to find an expert on a subject. **Messenger** or personal post is effective when asking for help from a known expert. While trying to find a solution is usually necessary to send an image referring to the problem or when it has to do with procedures video is a useful way of showing the errors. Thus, editor for posting and messaging should support these types in addition to the text content.

Functionalities:

- Post text/video/photo on public or private
- Messenger text/video/photo to a single person/team

b. Questions & Answers tool

Workers should be supported by an environment where they can exchange knowledge/experience and best practices upon specific procedures concerning their continuously training. This environment should support new recruits who are looking for answers, employees that need to execute procedures that don't usually perform them from the same or another department/unit, as well as employees that need to execute a less frequent action in the workflow which may be forgotten.

Experienced workers should be able to share their knowledge upon technical issues while the less experienced employees should be able to ask for support from co-workers in a safe support-oriented environment. Thus, users should be able to **ask a question** and **answer questions**. It is worth specifying that, the editor for answers and questions should support text, image and video upload. Then, it is useful to categorize these questions and answers with **tags** in order to be quickly accessible from the users when help needed immediately. **Categorizing** questions and answers help in forming a **documentation** where users can find answers on what they are looking for even if they don't submit a question. Questions and answers should be available at all times so that the workers are able to increase their knowledge at any time. Additionally, with these procedures being available at all times, future employees could have access to the established practices and the practices that are currently being formed as well as to their content of formation so that they can avoid repetitions, past mistakes and they are able to contribute more effectively to the progression of processes. For this reason, for every published element from users (questions, answers, comments) date and time should be presented.

With the content of the documentation platform being formed by the users, it is ensured that the platform's content is reformed according to the needs of the factory while they are changing. In order to ensure that the documentation platform will offer high quality support to its users according to the current needs a **voting system** should be implemented in order for the users to vote the most useful questions and answers. Voting system allows the users to express their opinion about a question or an answer and express their interest on a subject. For additional exchange of ideas and discussion on best practices, users should be able to **comment** the answers given.

While this section of the platform aims to be used from those looking for support on specific procedures that should be immediately given, a **search engine** should be available. Additionally, procedures that are available for practicing skills in training AR applications should be reminded to the users, while often an on-hand approach is the best way of learning new things.

Functionalities:

- Ask a question
- Answer a question
- Comment an answer
- Vote
- Documentation
- Editor for video, image, text
- Tags and Categories

- Search engine
- Date and time
- Training Apps reminder

2.3.1.2 ***UC-4.2 Acquire work schedule and sequence of actions***

According to users' needs the schedule that may change many times during day should be clear and easily accessible (D1.2, 6.5.4).

Workers use the Social Collaboration Platform in order to:

- View the schedule
- Post the schedule
- Send the schedule in team or network
- Send the schedule to employees that are coming on the next shift
- Get informed immediately when a change is conducted

Users can publish schedule changes through the Communication tool with the possibility to publish on the network or on a certain team in order to avoid confusions. With the asynchronously communication that a messenger support the schedule is easily accessible at any time. Additionally, when a change on schedule is posted, an important notification should inform the user immediately. Pending user trials of the initial version of the collaboration platform, integration of the schedule with a dedicated interactive web user interface will be tested in the next version of the platform.

Functionalities:

Communication tool

- Post
- Messenger
- Notifications for schedule changes

2.3.1.3 ***UC-6.3 Knowledge sharing among workers based on advanced reasoning***

Employees while using AR tools in shop floor need to ask for support from their co-workers. Through the Social Collaboration Platform and more specifically through the Communication Tool and Questions & Answers Tool this can be supported.

2.3.2 ***Social Collaboration Platform Tools***

Communication Tool represents a social network that connects the workers with each other and reinforces communication and collaboration among workers. This tool additionally supports the need of the users to exchange off-work content in order to have a pleasant time during work. Through communication tool users have access to the questions & answers tool.

Questions & Answers Tool represents a gamified forum environment where the employees are able to exchange knowledge and experience as well as share and seek for support from co-workers through gamified processes. A documentation is formed while the users contribute to the content of the platform in order to be available in all times.

All of the gamification outcomes from these three and other tools are presented at the Communication Tool.

Figure 8: Communication Tool

3 REQUIREMENTS

This chapter presents the user needs and requirements, which are related to developed concepts in this Deliverable. The requirements were tracked in JIRA. They are an outcome of the ideation process described in Chapter 4 and are also input to several iterations of this ideation process.

Table 3 lists the identified user needs to which we refer in Chapter 4. For the sake of a better overview, lists only the open requirements, which are currently still under consideration. The complete list of requirements containing all fields can be found in Deliverable D1.1 - User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines, second iteration, Annex 7. They can be identified, using the key field. Please note that the currently duplicated and out of scope requirements were decided to be out of scope during the ideation process. So, they are relevant for Chapter 4 as well.

Table 3: Overview of user needs, which were created during the ideation process of T2.3

Key	Summary	Linked Issues	Description
SAFA-210	The user needs to know the reason of rejection of his suggestion		The rejection status should be clear. The user expects a minimum length of feedback upon rejection of his suggestion.
SAFA-204	Personal statistics available to the users		{Quote} With the badge there will be possible to see your own statistics, and prove that this accepted suggestions are yours. {quote}
SAFA-196	The user needs to know the first feedback on the submitted suggestion soon after the suggestion has been submitted		{quote} I would wait one week for feedback on my suggestion. (Not for implementation, but feedback). If one week passes, I will assume the suggestion was not read at all. {quote}

Key	Summary	Linked Issues	Description
SAFA-193	Time duration availability of the suggestions	SAFA-194, SAFA-195	<p>The user needs to know how long the suggestion has already been there, in order to evaluate possible next steps.</p> <p>{quote} For example, I write a new suggestion. Date and time should be recorded. {quote}</p>
SAFA-192	Association of the workers' names with their suggestions		<p>Workers are encouraged to make suggestions to improve the existing process or even come up with new ideas. Some workers want to take credit for their suggestions by putting their name on it.</p> <p>{quote} "Would be good to have an optional "Your Name" field." {quote}</p> <p>According to them, they should be able to leave their name or identity behind so that they can claim rewards for it later.</p>
SAFA-176	The system shall provide efficient means for finding the assembly parts of a battery belonging to an order in order to collocate them for the next step where they get assembled		<p>Currently, the operator responsible for the first step of the traction battery assembly process at Sunlight gets a printed list of articles. The articles in the list are represented by figures (numbers). The worker needs to manually compare the number in the list to each of the articles physically present on the shop floor until the particular article has been found. This procedure is quite tiresome and boring. It could be made more efficient and even maybe fun.</p>
SAFA-175	The operator needs to know that the positive outcomes of their work are connected to their name in order to feel honored	SAFA-91, SAFA-92, SAFA-106, SAFA-144	<p>Operators enjoy seeing positive outcomes of their work and their name being related to these good results. Seeing their important contribution to the overall production and being honored, by being connected to these valuable outcomes, makes them feel good, proud and satisfied. It leads to higher identification with the product and leads to being more motivated at work (and thus probably perform better as stated in SAFA-92).</p>

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Key	Summary	Linked Issues	Description
SAFA-174	Continuous update of the operators' skills	SAFA-150	<p>Operators like to train others (it is a motivator) and they have expertise in special tasks or topics where they can train.</p> <p>This can be "advertised" so that other trainees or operators who search for training on those tasks or topics can approach them.</p>
SAFA-173	The operator needs to know that they work according to schedule in order to feel satisfied	SAFA-152	<p>Some workers at Sunlight pointed out that knowing they work well, particularly that their work meets the schedule makes them feel happy. Some delays in production instead (e.g. when some materials are missing) lead to stress.</p> <p>In cases when their work can be improved, there is a need for appropriate feedback and guidance on how exactly to improve (without criticism!).</p>
SAFA-171	All tasks should have priority and criticality ranks	SAFA-89, SAFA-170	<p>A great motivator for workers is the feeling that the work they do is a highly important contribution to the overall production process. The user interviews at Sunlight revealed that the awareness that the working step the workers are involved in is an important one, makes them feel more motivated and satisfied at work. Therefore, the importance of the particular work step needs to be made clear for the worker conducting that step.</p>
SAFA-170	The operator or the trainee needs to know details about the future usage and usefulness of the currently produced product in order to see their contribution to society	SAFA-171, SAFA-89	<p>An important motivator is to know what workers actually do their work for. The user and stakeholder interviews at Sunlight revealed that workers want to contribute to society by doing useful stuff.</p>
SAFA-156	The operator needs to be prepared for dealing with risks, dangers and emergencies at any time at work in order to ensure their and other workers' safety		<p>Knowing well the safety procedures is very crucial in such safety-critical environments as factories. Feeling that you and others really know them is very crucial for wellbeing at a factory. However, things (like safety guidelines) learned in safety courses are often forgotten after some time.</p>

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Key	Summary	Linked Issues	Description
SAFA-155	Real-time access to necessary knowledge for tasks		Sometimes operators need to help other departments. Then, they have to do tasks they are not trained for.
SAFA-154	Continuous access to training procedures		You forget tasks that you do not do often.
SAFA-153	The worker at Sunlight needs to have food from outside the canteen available during the late shifts in order to eat during the breaks		The canteen at Sunlight works only in the morning. This is a problem for the later shifts, especially at night.
SAFA-152	The operator needs to have current schedule available in order to work accordingly	SAFA-173	<p>The work schedule at Sunlight changes frequently during the week.</p> <p>Completing the work according to schedule contributes to satisfaction of the operators.</p> <p>Currently, this requires checking the schedule at least once per day (usually once in the beginning of the shift). The most of the operators at the Traction Battery Assembly division get a printed version of the schedule. Only at the last position in the assembly process, at the final quality assurance and packaging, there is a computer available that allows for more frequent checks of the schedule. If unexpected changes happen during a shift, the appropriate foreman gets informed and manages the situation accordingly.</p>

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Key	Summary	Linked Issues	Description
SAFA-151	The operator needs to know who can help with a particular issue in order to get in contact with that person	SAFA-101, SAFA-149, SAFA-99, SAFA-100, SAFA-150	<p>Sometimes operators need help with certain issues they encounter during the work, and it is often the case that someone of their co-workers is indeed experienced in the particular topic. If they knew who of their colleagues is experienced with such problems, they would be able to approach the respective co-workers directly.</p> <p>The knowledge about this is can be provided by colleagues (SAFA-150). The operator just has to know which colleague to contact.</p>
SAFA-150	The operator needs to be prepared for providing information with what kind of issues they can offer help in order to advertise their skills	SAFA-101, SAFA-107, SAFA-174, SAFA-97, SAFA-99, SAFA-100, SAFA-151	<p>Operators like helping each other. It increases the satisfaction. Moreover, helping others brings diversity to the workplace.</p> <p>Currently, the information about the skills of the workers is kept in the minds of the appropriate foremen.</p> <p>Sometimes it is however helpful to make these skills and expertise in special tasks transparent to everyone. This can be "advertised" so that other operators who search for help for those tasks can approach them directly.</p>
SAFA-149	The system should be able to manage all the open tasks	SAFA-99, SAFA-151	Operators can take over some tasks at idle times. For this, they need to know which tasks are open or where help is needed.
SAFA-148	Human-Resources toolkit shall efficient manage idle times		Operators can have idle times during which they could do other things. Since it is not clear how long a particular idle time lasts, it is not possible to do other things and be back in time when the actual work continues. Doing other things contributes to diversity at work, which in turn contributes to satisfaction at work.

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Key	Summary	Linked Issues	Description
SAFA-147	The foreman needs to be prepared for providing feedback on suggestions for improvement in order to create a productive dialog between the workers and decision-makers on this topic	SAFA-105, SAFA-146, SAFA-145	Workers who suggested an improvement need feedback what happened to that improvement. So, decision-makers need a possibility to provide such feedback.
SAFA-146	Release answers/feedback on suggestions for improvements to operators	SAFA-105, SAFA-97, SAFA-147	If workers just see that their suggestions for improvement are not applied without knowing the reason, they get demotivated.
SAFA-145	The foreman or the operator needs to be prepared for providing positive feedback to others in order to motivate them	SAFA-91, SAFA-144, SAFA-147	Getting positive feedback from others is a major motivator at work.
SAFA-144	The operator needs to have positive feedback available in order to feel good about his work	SAFA-91, SAFA-92, SAFA-145, SAFA-175	Positive feedback about the own work is a major motivator.
SAFA-108	The system shall improve teamwork through optimal task allocation		It is usually not possible to distribute work in a way that everybody's personal goals are fulfilled. The goal is to optimize teamwork and not to fulfill personal goals.
SAFA-107	The system shall utilize skills and capabilities of the workers available for optimal work assignment	SAFA-150	Every individual worker fits better to some workplaces and worse to other workplaces and tasks. Thus, the supervisor & the HR Re-adaptation tool will optimally distribute tasks.
SAFA-106	The operator needs to have a metric available in order to assess their work	SAFA-91, SAFA-92, SAFA-104, SAFA-175	Assessing own work is necessary for understanding what can be done better. A metric helps to assess the work by providing a means of comparison with a goal or reference standard.

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Key	Summary	Linked Issues	Description
SAFA-105	The system shall provide means of submitting suggestions for improvements available, in order to contribute to modernization and overall improvement of working conditions	SAFA-146, SAFA-88, SAFA-97, SAFA-147	A working process for workers suggesting improvements is helpful for the overall process of the factory (benefit from management point of view). At the same time, workers benefit from it as they feel heard, involved and valuable, also feeling a kind of power to change something. Additionally, such a process for suggestions for improvement can be rewarded separately. In general, it must be assured that the workers know how to provide suggestions.
SAFA-104	The operator needs to have concrete feedback available for what can be done better in order to improve	SAFA-91, SAFA-106	After having assessed work results, details about the assessment and concrete suggestions for improvement are source for process improvements
SAFA-103	The process supervisor needs to know the details of his work process in order to start working		The work of process supervisors is not self-explanatory. The details of their work processes can change on a daily base. Moreover, employees who start working as process supervisors need an introduction into the work process.
SAFA-102	The operator needs to have means for intellectual stimulation available in order to avoid boredom and monotony		Monotonous work is considered as source for boredom and inattentiveness. This can lead to critical situations, lower product quality and demotivation of workers. Often, intellectual resources are free in parallel to these monotonous tasks.
SAFA-101	Different opinions shall be exchanged during the operation of a task	SAFA-97, SAFA-99, SAFA-100, SAFA-150, SAFA-151	This is desired in case of meeting with problems. Spontaneously and directly asking co-workers for help was requested in the interviews.
SAFA-100	The operator or process supervisor needs to have opportunities to help their co-workers available (when they need help) in order to	SAFA-101, SAFA-97, SAFA-99, SAFA-150, SAFA-	Helping others makes people feel useful and valued. It is considered as a source of motivation and satisfaction. Thus, there is a need to provide opportunities for them to help their co-workers.

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Key	Summary	Linked Issues	Description
	feel useful and valued	151	
SAFA-99	The operator or process supervisor needs to know the problems of others in order to be able to help them	SAFA-101, SAFA-149, SAFA-97, SAFA-100, SAFA-150, SAFA-151	Prerequisite for providing help is the awareness that help is needed and an indication of what is the problem.
SAFA-98	The operator or process supervisor needs to be prepared for communicating with co-workers in order to discuss private topics	SAFA-97	Private discussions are good for teamwork, well-being and motivation at work. They are also often starting point for work related discussions, which again can lead to problem solving and process optimization.
SAFA-97	The operator or process supervisor needs to be prepared for discussing production issues with co-workers in order to solve or optimize these issues	SAFA-101, SAFA-105, SAFA-146, SAFA-98, SAFA-99, SAFA-100, SAFA-150	Interaction and discussion with co-workers are a valuable source for solving problems and optimizing procedures. These discussions already happen but are restricted to moments (at Sunlight usually during shift change) when people physically meet.
SAFA-96	The operator needs to have supporting documentation on daily procedures in order to perform the procedures accurately		<p>Operators at CERTH-CPERI conduct quite complex tasks, e.g. preparing a unit for an experiment, or starting up and shutting down of the units. Although particular units and experiments can be quite different, there are some standard procedures or workflows the operators need to follow from time to time. There is a need for some kind of documentation of these procedures or workflows, e.g. guidelines or checklists, since humans tend to forget things.</p> <p>Procedure guidelines are a prerequisite for procedure quality assurance as processes can be compared to them.</p>

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Key	Summary	Linked Issues	Description
SAFA-95	The platform should be inform the actors about the kind of the running processes of a pilot plant		The layout of a pilot plant is quite complex: not all parts are in use for a particular chemical process that is implemented in the pilot plant. Thus, the operators and the technicians should be informed from the platform for the kind of the processes that are currently running at the pilot plant
SAFA-94	The operator needs to know who is responsible for a sounding alarm in order to know whom to address	SAFA-93	There are different alarms at frequent times and it is not always clear who is responsible for solving/managing the issue, and whom to address for a particular alarm in case communication is needed.
SAFA-93	Alarms shall be accompanied with a description	SAFA-94	There are different alarms at frequent times and it is not always clear how to behave for a particular alarm.
SAFA-92	The operator needs to be able to access the work results their name is related to in order to perform better	SAFA-91, SAFA-106, SAFA-144, SAFA-175	In order to assess the own work results, one needs to have access to them. Furthermore, it is necessary to know to which results the own name is associated. Having the own name associated to good work results is a motivating factor.
SAFA-91	The operator needs to know how to improve in order to be able to increase the quality of their work and thus be more satisfied	SAFA-92, SAFA-104, SAFA-106, SAFA-144, SAFA-145, SAFA-175	Knowing that the quality of personal contribution is constantly growing is a very important factor for satisfaction at work. In addition, the process of increasing of the quality is highly related to the process of learning, which presence generally also contributes to satisfaction. A prerequisite for such improvement of work results is however, the knowledge of what exactly needs to be done in order to improve (_formative_ feedback).
SAFA-90	The operator needs to have artifacts available in their workplace that are not directly related to the actual work in order to feel more comfortable in their work environment		Elements from leisure time evoke pleasant feelings and create positive emotions at work that are known from private locations. Not every private artifact is suitable to be introduced. Workplace requirements need to be considered.

SATISFACTORY

Key	Summary	Linked Issues	Description
SAFA-89	The operator or the trainee needs to know what the currently produced product will be used for and how important the particular working step is, in order to feel more satisfied at work	SAFA-171, SAFA-170	An important motivator is to know what workers actually do their work for. The user interviews revealed that workers want to contribute to society by doing useful stuff. Furthermore the responsibility and important of the particular work step and therefore for the worker conducting that step needs to be made clear.
SAFA-88	The operator needs to know how to provide suggestions for improvement, in order to contribute to the enhancement of the efficiency of their work and thus feel more satisfied	SAFA-105	A working process for workers suggesting improvements is helpful for the overall process of the factory (benefit from management point of view). At the same time, workers benefit from it as they feel heard, involved and valuable, also feeling a kind of power to change something. Additionally, such a process for suggestions for improvement can be rewarded separately. In general, it must be assured that the workers know how to provide suggestions.
SAFA-87	The operator needs to know how dirty his hands are (at a factory with invisible chemicals) in order to be sensitized to wash them more frequently		When working with chemicals, not washing your hands can result in safety issues, e.g., when you eat. Sometimes washing the hands is forgotten or it is not clear that hands are contaminated, because the chemicals (e.g. lead at Sunlight) are invisible for the eye.
SAFA-3	Mechanical operator needs to have safe and efficient means for lifting and moving heavy mechanical components available in order to relocate them from workbench to pallet		At COMAU, Robotics shop floor operators say that the fixtures available to move heavy mechanical components from workbench to pallet are not safe and efficient enough, because currently they are using belts and chain, which are generic tools that do not fix the parts properly (parts could move/rotate/fall down if not properly fixed).

Table 4: Overview of currently active requirements, which were defined during the ideation process of T2.3

Key	Summary	Description	Fit Criterion	Requirement Type
SAFA-221	The gamification framework should allow workers to participate individually as well as in teams	The participants should be allowed to take part on their own or in the forms of teams.	The gamification framework provides the functionality that allows workers to participate individually as well as in teams	Non-Functional
SAFA-220	Other SatisFactory components shall submit points of participants to the gamification framework	The subcomponents of the satisfactory should be able to submit points of participants based on the tasks they perform	The gamification framework provides the functionality allow the subcomponents of satisfactory to submit scores	Functional
SAFA-218	No participant of the gamification shall be exposed as loser	The gamification framework shall ensure that no participant is exposed as a loser.	No participant is exposed as loser	Non-Functional
SAFA-217	The gamification framework must support PBL	PBL. Points, badges and leader boards are some of the most effective game elements in gamification. The gamification framework should support these elements	The gamification framework supports PBL	Non-Functional - operational
SAFA-215	Gamification must be presented in several subcomponents of SatisFactory	Gamification should not only be present just as a separate system but it should be present in several subcomponents of satisfactory	Gamification is present in several subcomponents of satisfactory	Non-Functional

Key	Summary	Description	Fit Criterion	Requirement Type
SAFA-211	The suggestion submission form shall be in similar format as the pre-existing manual system	A manual system to submit suggestions for improvement already exists. The form to submit a suggestion in the suggestions platform should have the same format.	The product has the suggestion submission form in the same format as the pre-existing manual system	Non-Functional
SAFA-208	Open suggestions shall be sent to the decision makers	Decision makers should be notified periodically about open suggestions that they need to decide upon.	The system provides a functionality to inform the decision makers about open suggestions	Non-Functional - operational
SAFA-207	Suggestions system should support suggestion categories	The suggestions are assigned to different categories depending on their relevancy. These categories are predefined and are to be provided by the factory management.	The product has the suggestion categories provided by the factory management	Non-Functional - operational
SAFA-206	The product shall keep the prize detail separate from the system	The prize or award details associated with the contributions should be stored separately	The product keeps the prize detail separate from the system	Non-Functional
SAFA-205	Evaluation of a contribution will support point scale	A point scale for the evaluation of a contribution could be used, in order to assess the importance of the contribution. A more important contribution gets more points.	The system provides a functionality to define a point scale for the evaluation of a contribution	Non-Functional

Key	Summary	Description	Fit Criterion	Requirement Type
SAFA-203	Suggestions filtering support	There can be different kinds of filtering and summarizing the suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show all accepted • Show all rejected 	The system provides a functionality to filter the suggestions	Non-Functional
SAFA-202	Suggestions will be sorted by submission date	Suggestions sorted by submission date associates a meaning to the way suggestions are being displayed. The latest suggestions should be displayed first	The product has the suggestions sorted by submission date	Non-Functional - operational
SAFA-200	The UIs should be user-friendly	"<" back button should be better visible. At least there should be more space between the title of the category and the arrow	The product has visible buttons	Non-Functional - look and feel
SAFA-198	All UI interaction parts should be clearly visible	The button should have clear text. Clear and easily understandable terms should be used to describe the purpose of that button.	The product has clear button text	Non-Functional
SAFA-197	UIs shall be in the formal language of the deployment country	The UIs should be in the native language of the employees so that it is easier for them to understand the terms used.	The product UIs are in the native language of the employees	Non-Functional - usability

Key	Summary	Description	Fit Criterion	Requirement Type
SAFA-143	Support feedback answers on suggestions for improvement	It is not always clear to workers what happens to their suggestions for improvement, i.e. they just see that a suggestions is not applied but do not know if the suggestion has reached the ear of the management or if it was rejected and for which reason	The suggestions for improvement system provides the following feedback for each suggestion: - when it has reached the decider - the decider's decision upon it - if it was rejected, the reason for rejection	Functional
SAFA-140	Support mobile users	Most workers at the shop floor don't have a fixed location like an office and they change their place of work often		Non-Functional - operational
SAFA-137	Support flexible deviations from plan	Work timings and breaks are flexibly and spontaneously adapted when the situation requires it	The system continues working normal when workers change their actions compared to the work plan	Non-Functional - operational
SAFA-136	The system shall be applicable when workers wear a mask	The system will be operational in cases where workers wear masks		Non-Functional - usability
SAFA-135	The system shall not influence workers' carefulness	"It is easy to hurt yourself if you don't watch what you are doing"	After 2 weeks of operation, no accident is reported which is caused by reduced carefulness due to the system	Non-Functional - usability
SAFA-134	The system shall be able to be adapted to different shifts	Sunlight is working in two shifts with weekly rotation.	The system can adapt to a worker when changing the shift	Non-Functional - operational

Key	Summary	Description	Fit Criterion	Requirement Type
SAFA-133	The system shall have access to the most recent work schedules	Work plan and schedule changes occur frequently (several times a week), so the system has always access to the most recent work schedules		Non-Functional - operational
SAFA-132	The product shall not restrict workers' autonomy	Workers have a level of autonomy that they don't want to be curbed	In an evaluation, at least 80% of the participants state that the system does not restrict their autonomy	Non-Functional
SAFA-131	Competition shall be informal and friendly	Competing with others is a motivator for doing better work. However, if it is performed too dogged and fussy, it can lead to demotivation as well	In an evaluation questionnaire, at least 80% of the participants report a positive attitude towards the competition	Non-Functional
SAFA-120	The communication product shall be open for non-work related content	In order to boost teamwork, motivation, interaction and satisfaction, communication system shall not be restricted to work related content		Constraint - purpose
SAFA-118	The product shall provide means to teach co-workers	Teaching co-workers is considered valuable for teacher and learner	The system provides means of teaching co-workers	Functional

Key	Summary	Description	Fit Criterion	Requirement Type
SAFA-117	The system shall support inter-change of best practices between departments and units	The knowledge exchange between departments and unit can be less intensive than within a unit. Other units can benefit from best practices as well. Means to transfer descriptions of best practices between departments and units is provided.		Functional
SAFA-115	Real-time visualization of the pilot plants operation data related to the training process	The operation of the pilot plant is visible in a SCADA system but not directly inside the shop floor. Knowing the operation could be helpful to the trainers.		Functional
SAFA-19	The platform will include a personal protection equipment usage reminder	All actions within the shop floor must be performed with the necessary safety measures. Thus, the system will remind the actor which measures must be used according to the performed action	All actors involved at the shop floor would be reminded to use the necessary personal safety measures such as gloves, helmet, glasses working aprons etc. when working at the shop floor	Functional
SAFA-18	SatisFactory tools shall give detailed description of selected maintenance actions	Maintenance procedures will be recorded in order to be available to actors when necessary. They could be access via a tablet or a pc and actors will be guided how to perform the specific action	All maintenance actions and procedures could be recorded	Functional

Key	Summary	Description	Fit Criterion	Requirement Type
SAFA-17	The tools shall be able to successfully exchange data with the existing infrastructure at the shop floors	SatisFactory platform will enhance the existing platforms at the shop floors in order to offer to the actors a better way to perform some of their activities	Documents from the product shall be compatible with the existing collaboration platforms and vice versa	Non-Functional - operational
SAFA-13	The tools and applications must be 24/7 operational	CPERI is operating 24h each day, so all the tools and applications that will be installed at the shop floor must be continuously operational	The product is available 24 hours a day.	Non-Functional - operational
SAFA-4	The HMIs of the platform shall be attractive and easy to use	The HMIs that will be created within the SatisFactory project must be user friendly in order to be easy to use from any actor who is involved with the project.	A sampling of representative young job-seekers are, after five minutes of using the product, are willing to use it further and recommend the product to their friends.	Non-Functional - look and feel

In order to group requirements topic-wise, we introduced a label fields to the requirement tool. So, everybody was able to add one or more labels to a requirement. New labels could be created by simply entering them as text. After this, the new label appeared as menu bar for all other requirements so that the same label could be easily assigned to further requirements. A click on a label filters all requirements with the same label. Figure 9 shows the distribution of these labels.

Figure 9: Labels assigned to the related requirements

3.1 REQUIREMENTS TO GAMIFICATION FRAMEWORK MAPPING

The following table describes how different requirements have been mapped to various aspects of the Gamification Framework.

Table 5: The Gamification Framework addresses identified requirements

Key	Summary	Application
SAFA-62	Motivate the individuals (especially younger generation people) to be engaged in a working environment. This mainly consist in the introduction in the semantic of the UI some elements that derive from the experience of gaming (in particular those that regard the context of multi-role competitive experiences)	The gamification framework is used to create games by the external systems. By participating in these games, workers can earn points and as a result achieve their goals. The workers are also able to view their individual and cumulative scores which serves as a major motivation factor
SAFA-	Develop a training platform to demonstrate	The training platform can be one of the

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Key	Summary	Application
80	production processes to the trainees. The training platform will incorporate augmented reality devices such as glasses and context aware tablet or smartphone. In addition, by using gamification tools the training will be more attractive and interesting to the trainees.	external systems that can use the gamification framework to define as to how the workers can earn points and what goals can they achieve. It will make the training process more fun and engaging
SAFA-174	Operators like to train others (it is a motivator) and they have expertise in special tasks or topics where they can train. This can be "advertised" so that other trainees or operators who search for training on those tasks or topics can approach them.	Training others can also be an external system. Workers can attain points upon giving trainings to others.
SAFA-167	Washing hands effectively is important for health because of cleaning hands from lead. However, it is often forgotten. An ambient display could raise the awareness	Protect your Health is one of the external systems that utilizes the gamification framework to motivate the workers to wash their hands more often
SAFA-165	Training is requested for tasks that are not performed often or for tasks workers are sometimes assigned to in other departments, and for which they are not trained. Training for this could be done at idle times, so the time of performing the training should be determined by the worker	Training others can also be an external system. Workers can attain points upon giving trainings to others.
SAFA-161	Workers are happy to train others and have knowledge in specific tasks in which they are able to train others. The others need to know for which tasks to contact which person	Training others can also be an external system. Workers can attain points upon giving trainings to others.
SAFA-151	Sometimes operators need help with certain issues they encounter during the work, and it is often the case that someone of their co-workers is indeed experienced in the particular topic. If they knew who of their colleagues is experienced with such problems, they would be able to approach the respective co-workers directly.	The help platform can be an external system in which the workers can attain points upon providing help to others.
SAFA-147	The foreman needs to be prepared for providing feedback on suggestions for improvement in order to create a productive dialog between the workers and decision-makers on this topic	The foreman can attain points upon providing feedback using the suggestions for improvement platform as an external system to the gamification framework.
SAFA-	Competing with others is a motivator for	The concept of competition is applied by

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Key	Summary	Application
131	doing better work. However, if it is performed too dogged and fussy, it can lead to demotivation as well	implementing a winning streak via the digital screen. The workers compete with their own score that they accomplished the day before.
SAFA-120	In order to boost teamwork, motivation, interaction and satisfaction, communication system shall not be restricted to work related content	The sense of community is maintained by maintaining a single instance of gamification for all the external systems. So, everyone contributes to the same collective score of all the workers of the factory by performing any task related to any of the external systems linked to with the gamification framework.
SAFA-100	Helping others makes people feel useful and valued. It is considered as a source of motivation and satisfaction. Thus, there is a need to provide opportunities for them to help their co-workers.	In order to motivate workers to help each other, it can be linked with the gamification platform and the workers can earn points every time they help someone.
SAFA-109	Receiving training is a general motivator. In addition, training for issues that are not directly related to the normal work activities is requested, especially if it helps for next jobs or generally in life. This can be, e.g., language training	Training others can also be an external system. Workers can attain points upon giving trainings to others.
SAFA-130	The product shall provide fun content Jokes and fun are identified as important contributors to well-being, team building and satisfaction at work and against monotony	This requirement maps indirectly to the gamification framework where the whole purpose of applying this concept is to create an enjoyable working environment for the worker by simply applying different elements of gamification in their daily work routine.
SAFA-21	The product shall boost collaboration.	Gamification provides a collaborative environment by having team games
SAFA-25	Creation of social interaction platform	Gamification promotes social interaction by motivating the workers to compete in teams against other teams and also by introducing a winning streak

4 IDEATION PROCESS

This chapter describes how the ideas to increase the attractiveness of factories for the SatisFactory workers evolved. It describes the results of major iterations. Section 2.1 presents the underlying methodology.

4.1 FIRST MAJOR ITERATION

As first iteration, the collected knowledge and statements from worker interviews were gathered and clustered. Then, for each item, ideas were generated. Table 6 shows the statements, from which kind of worker it is originated, the category to which it is clustered and the generated idea.

Table 6: Results of the first major ideation iteration

User Group	Citation	Category	Issue / Idea Description
Operator	"You need to know a lot of English or German"	Training	Provide further training for not related work issues. Something that helps in next jobs, or generally in life, or at current job in additional interesting fields or work situations Use GlassUp device for translation of languages
Operator	"People don't wash their hands"	Safety	Possibly visualize if hands are washed thoroughly with technology
Foreman	"The company is open to suggestions"	Teamwork	A platform where you can place your suggestions for improvement. e.g. "Kummerkasten" with direct line to management. e.g. area where you can try out suggestions. e.g. you get rewarded with free time to test something
Trainee	"I like to contribute to society by doing useful stuff" "I like the current working place as it has more responsibility" / "Being responsible for important production step" / filling in critical position	Satisfaction	Tell stories what the currently produced product will be used for and how important the particular working step is
Operator	Knowing the meaning of alarms and who is responsible	Problems to solve	

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User Group	Citation	Category	Issue / Idea Description
	would be good.		
Automation IT Technician	"Sometimes I don't go out in fire drills. I have more important things to do"	Safety	Gamification: First out wins a price. Last in is burned
Operator	Need to have a mapping of the path and flow of material in the plant	Problems to solve	Show path using AR
Operator	Need for guidelines for daily procedures		
Operator, Process Supervisor	Experience exchange between process operators should be improved and transfer of best practices between different departments or units "I like to teach others" Asking for opinion of others "I feel good when I help and when I get help" Private topics are discussed either in the canteen, smoking place "Discuss production issues"		Social collaboration platform
Operator	Make Operators do something more intellectual than just push buttons, e.g. writing manuals	Monotony at Work / Challenges and Variety	Tool to stimulate intellectual activities, related to current work. (e.g. quiz duel)
Process supervisor	"Nobody showed me the ropes (how to work)"		Introductory Mentoring for newcomers, e.g. electronically supported
Foreman	"If we put plants someone will water them with acid."	Workplace (statements)	Making workplace more cozy by introducing artifacts that are not directly related to the actual work (and even come from leisure time)
all	Soccer is the most popular hobby	Hobby	This observation can be used in other ideas, in particular by developing gamification concepts, e.g. betting game
Operator	"I like to surf on the Internet at home"	Hobby	This observation can be used in other ideas, e.g. for providing surfing

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User Group	Citation	Category	Issue / Idea Description
			opportunities at idle times
Operator	"Not boring", monotony"	"Avoid Monotony at Work / Challenges and Variety	Unused physical or mental capacities could be occupied by some interesting or fun activities, e.g. occupied hands vs. free mind capacity
Operator	"I want stuff to be perfect if connected with my name"	Satisfaction	"Favored worker of the week" (popular / favorite / likes / best spirit) Hero of the week
Operator	"Teamwork is a key to goal" Shift goals	Teamwork & Satisfaction	Team / Shift with the best spirit -> Spirit prize
Operator	"Skills and capabilities are rewarded"	Satisfaction	Central pool with where everybody can enter their skills and make them public, e.g. something like a skill market
Operator	"Smoking breaks, thus everyone smokes" "More frequent breaks"	Satisfaction	
Operator	"At the end of 1st hour they told me the last guy lasted just 1 hour: you are doing fine."	Satisfaction	Provide statistics to a worker where he is in the top range
Operator	"The company is open to suggestions" "I was told we do it this way. If you find another way, do it. If it is better we will follow."	Communication	Platform to provide suggestions easier / faster / more direct to the concerned parties / workers
Operator	Getting concrete feedback for what can be done better is important	Communication	
Operator	"Jokes break the monotony of the job"		Funny contents in social platform: like exchange jokes, probably context-dependent (location, time etc.) and select the funniest employee of the week
Operator, Maintenance at CERTH	"Feel stress about missing materials and blocked orders." No barcode system available for dealing with labeled items		Smart inventory and resource management tools
Operator	Pocket contents: To-do List;		Remember the milk tool. E.g., speak

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User Group	Citation	Category	Issue / Idea Description
	Problems to tell supervisor/next shift; Timings		things to remember to small tool. Automatic transcription. Read them when needed
Operator	"Once you get feedback, it is easier to work"		Button associated to work task, where others can provide you with likes. Extension: Provide more detailed feedback. E.g., attach button to task. Buttons gives you URL. You provide detailed feedback under URL later.
Operator	"New ideas are discussed but I think they don't reach the ears of management" "Some ideas are not given time and space to develop and some automation is not considered"		Suggestion system makes sure that people know what happened to their suggestion, i.e., deciders need to give a reason for decision to system.
Operator	Workers need to compare long number on order list to the numbers on the battery boxes. No barcodes are used. This is time-consuming, tiring and under their qualification		Introduce barcodes for managing flow of materials and tasks
Operator	Operators have idle times and often don't know how long they last		Provide feedback how long idle time lasts Provide a list of tasks that need to be done for people to choose from
Operator, Foreman, Trainee	"I am happy to train others"		Provide a forum where people can either offer help for a specific tasks or ask for help
Operator	"The schedule changes during the week. I have to check very frequently"		Way to faster access the current work schedule. E.g. screen at workplace
Operator, Foreman, Trainee	The canteen works only in the morning. Problem for the later shifts, especially in the night		Central system to organize food delivery. Everybody can place his orders. Maybe deadline until when it is sent. Maybe choose from list of pre-defined delivery services and list of pre-defined food once the delivery service is chosen
Operator	You forget tasks that you do		Online training courses

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User Group	Citation	Category	Issue / Idea Description
	not do often People sometime have to help out other departments. Then they need to do tasks they are not trained for		
Operator	"We get training only for critical changes but even that is informal"		Document every task and keep it up-to-date. Provide access to this knowledge for everybody. Each task documentation is led by a worker
Operator	"Older people don't remember things they learned in the safety course. " "They don't wash hands"	Safety	Ambient display that visualizes amount of lead concentration at toilet door handle. (To increase awareness to wash hands. Is like indicator for group cleanness)

Apart from the results above, there were a few general insights that can be relevant for several developed concepts. These are:

- Trustworthiness towards workers is important ("They never ask why I need new clothes" --> "I like when they trust me")
- Workers like informal friendly competition ("At the end of 1st hour they told me the last guy lasted just 1 hour: you are doing fine.")
- Operators have friends in other departments
- Mobile phones are widely used in the factory
- Important aspects are self-determination / autonomy at work

4.2 SECOND MAJOR ITERATION

In the second iteration, the ideas from the first iteration were refined into rough concepts. During this process, also a short name was assigned. Furthermore, it was checked how the concepts fit to the SatisFactory use cases and business scenarios in order to align with the overall project progress. The IDs of column 3 in Table 7 refer to the first version of Deliverable D1.2 - Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description, Chapter 5 and Section 6.5.

Table 7: Results of the second major ideation iteration

Short name	Concept	Related use case	SF	Covered aspect
Protect your Health	Visualize the level of washed hands at door handles for own hall and other halls. -> create competition between halls. Trigger measurement once a day. Need to check how measurement is possible	BSC-6.1		Gamification, Interfaces, Sensor

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Short name	Concept	Related SF use case	Covered aspect
	(sensors?).		
Quiz duel	<p>Dueled quiz is provided. Dedicated session after training for new employees. Alternative: Offer a dedicated session during work time, which people can enter voluntarily.</p> <p>Teams answer the questions as a team and play against another team. Rules like Quiz duel: One team selects a category and then answers 3 questions. Other team then has to answer the same questions and starts over with selecting a new category. Team with more correct answers wins after 6 rounds.</p> <p>The questions are connected to the work. This brings a training effect; workers learn while playing. The connection to the work is broad, for example, there can be questions about the boat for which the produced battery is used for. This increases the bond of worker and product/factory/company.</p> <p>Instead of textual questions, visual tasks that need to be solved in a group are provided. For example, assemble a battery. Next level: Assemble the boat for which the battery is used.</p>	BSC-4.3 for new employees to reflect on initial trainings	Gamification, Interfaces
Jokes platform	<p>Platform where jokes/links to funny content such as virals or interesting stories from the daily work can be uploaded. The content should increase satisfaction and team building first of all. Every week the funniest content of the week is awarded (the one with most clicks). -> positive feedback for the content provider. Then the other contents are erased. Always ordered by "last added" in order to have a fair rating mechanism</p> <p>Platform can be accessible inside factory (in areas where people pass by) in a public manner, e.g., public displays. This can enhance the work environment itself.</p>	UC-5.3	Gamification, Interfaces, Social interaction
Help platform	<p>Platform where workers can provide trainings for work-related or not work-related issues. Maybe screens in every hall. Trainings can be asynchronous, like videos that can be requested when time and the provider does not need to be available at that time. Or, live help can be requested which connects help provider with help requester</p>	BSC-2.1	Social collaboration, Interfaces
Knowledge	Platform where people can enter knowledge.	BSC- 1.1	Social

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Short name	Concept	Related use case	SF	Covered aspect
platform	Documented knowledge can be rated. Can be integrated in the help platform. Use tablet PC augmented reality platform.			collaboration, Interfaces
Suggestions for improvement	Platform where workers can enter their suggestions for improvement. Platform makes sure that suggestion reaches the decider (How?). Decider has to enter whether it was applied, whether it was applied with modification or whether it was not applied. In the latter case, the reason for rejection is mandatory. This information is fed back to the worker who entered the suggestion.	UC-5.1		Social collaboration, Interfaces
Food order	Tool for managing collective orders at food delivery services. A worker initializes a collective order. For this, he chooses from a list of food delivery services in the city and sets the time for placing individual orders to 1 hour. All workers who have subscribed to be interested in collective food orders receive a notification at their smartphones. Then he places his own order, choosing from a list of available food from the selected delivery service. Using the system, workers can add their order to the collective order. They can either browse the list of already ordered foods by their co-workers or "add one" (fast mode). Alternatively, they can select a food from the list provided by the selected delivery service. After the order time is run out, the possibility to add orders to the collective order is closed by the system and the collective order is transmitted to the delivery service			Social interaction, Interfaces
Story telling	Screens present information what a product is used for. The more details this story has, the more tangible it gets for the workers and they know why they are doing this work. For instance, the battery is used for a boat and the screen provides information about technical details of that boat, about the customer and for which purpose the boat is used.	BSC-4.1		Interfaces
AR path	Show path of material flow with AR glasses in shop floor mapped to the physical environment	BSC-5.3		Interfaces
Thank you	QR codes are added to the final product and customers are asked to say "thank you" to the Sunlight workers by executing the QR code. The "Thank you"-s are presented to the Sunlight workers. -> positive feedback. Customers can also be internal customers, i.e. departments that post-process parts	UC-5.2		Social interaction, Interfaces

Short name	Concept	Related use case	SF	Covered aspect
	from other departments can say thank you to the pre-processing department. Even more detailed individual workers can give “likes” to the work of co-workers.			
Identify assembly parts	So far, when battery needs to be assembled, worker gets a list of articles to use, gets them in form of numbers, then he needs to manually compare the number to each of the articles in front of him. Solution: barcode scanner. Even better solution would be to get articles already in correct order	BSC-4.1		Interfaces
Work schedule info screen	A screen at the workplace informs team about the current work schedule for the day, i.e. on which orders each member has to work	UC-4.2		Interfaces

4.3 THIRD MAJOR ITERATION

As next step, the concepts were elaborated and assigned to several aspects in order to assess them. This is summarized in Table 8. The related user needs refer to the ones described in Chapter 3 and are used to verify the relevance for the workers. The column goal identifies which goal was tried to be achieved with the concept. If there were problems with defining a goal for a particular concept, this would have been an indicator that the concept is useless.

Table 8: Results of the third major ideation iteration

Short Name	Concept	User Need	Goal
Protect your Health	Visualize the level of washed hands at door handles for own hall and other halls. -> create competition between halls. Trigger measurement once a day. Need to check how measurement is possible (sensors?).	SAFA-87 (SAFA-156)	Safety --- Healthcare Motivation to increase hygiene
Quiz duel	Dueld quiz is provided. Dedicated session after training for new employees. Alternative: Offer a dedicated session during work time, which people can enter voluntarily. Teams answer the questions as a team and play against another team. Rules like Quiz duel: One team selects a category and then answers 3 questions. Other team then has to answer the same questions and starts over with selecting a new category. Team with more correct answers wins after 6 rounds. The questions are connected to the work. This brings a training effect; workers learn while	(SAFA-102) (SAFA-154)	Training Teambuilding (when playing in teams) --- Strengthen the bond between the workers and the product Promote a deeper understanding of work related

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Short Name	Concept	User Need	Goal
	<p>playing. The connection to the work is broad, for example, there can be questions about the boat for which the produced battery is used for. This increases the bond of worker and product/factory/company.</p> <p>Instead of textual questions, visual tasks that need to be solved in a group are provided. For example, assemble a battery. Next level: Assemble the boat for which the battery is used.</p>		<p>topics</p> <p>(Provide an implicit technical training)</p>
Jokes platform	<p>Platform where jokes/links to funny content such as virals or interesting stories from the daily work can be uploaded. The content should increase satisfaction and team building first of all. Every week the funniest content of the week is awarded (the one with most clicks). -> positive feedback for the content provider. Then the other contents are erased. Always ordered by "last added" in order to have a fair rating mechanism</p> <p>Platform can be accessible inside factory (in areas where people pass by) in a public manner, e.g., public displays. This can enhance the work environment itself.</p>	SAFA-98	<p>Teamwork / Teambuilding</p> <p>Communication</p> <p>Satisfaction</p> <p>---</p> <p>Cultivate good relationship with colleagues</p> <p>Have fun</p>
Help platform	<p>Platform where workers can provide trainings for work-related or not work-related issues. Maybe screens in every hall. Trainings can be asynchronous, like videos that can be requested when time and the provider does not need to be available at that time. Or, live help can be requested which connects help provider with help requester</p>	<p>SAFA-100</p> <p>SAFA-155</p> <p>SAFA-102</p> <p>(SAFA-151)</p> <p>(SAFA-148)</p> <p>use during idle times</p> <p>(SAFA-149)</p> <p>take over a help task</p> <p>(SAFA-150)</p> <p>who can help</p> <p>(SAFA-154)</p> <p>cont. training</p>	<p>Training</p> <p>Teamwork</p> <p>---</p> <p>Provide help from colleagues on a personal level</p> <p>Create connection between co-workers</p> <p>Evoke feeling of being valuable and useful</p>
Knowledge	Platform where people can enter knowledge.	SAFA-100	Training

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Short Name	Concept	User Need	Goal
platform	Documented knowledge can be rated. Can be integrated in the help platform. Use tablet PC augmented reality platform.	SAFA-155	Teamwork
Suggestions for improvement	Platform where workers can enter their suggestions for improvement. Platform makes sure that suggestion reaches the decider (How?). Decider has to enter whether it was applied, whether it was applied with modification or whether it was not applied. In the latter case, the reason for rejection is mandatory. This information is fed back to the worker who entered the suggestion.	SAFA-105 SAFA-146	Satisfaction Organization Productivity Teamwork --- Enhance self-determination Support / appreciate creativity
Food order	Tool for managing collective orders at food delivery services. A worker initializes a collective order. For this, he chooses from a list of food delivery services in the city and sets the time for placing individual orders to 1 hour. All workers who have subscribed to be interested in collective food orders receive a notification at their smartphones. Then he places his own order, choosing from a list of available food from the selected delivery service. Using the system, workers can add their order to the collective order. They can browse the list of already ordered foods by their co-workers and “add one” (fast mode). Alternatively, they can select a food from the list provided by the selected delivery service. After the order time is run out, the possibility to add orders to the collective order is closed by the system and the collective order is transmitted to the delivery service	SAFA-153	Organization Satisfaction --- Provide basic comfort
Story telling	Screens present information what a product is used for. The more details this story has, the more tangible it gets for the workers and they know why they are doing this work. For instance, the battery is used for a boat and the screen provides information about technical details of that boat, about the customer and for which purpose the boat is used.	SAFA-170 SAFA-171 Based on reported great experiences! (UX)	Motivation --- Strengthen identification with work / product
AR path	Show path of material flow with AR glasses in shop floor mapped to the physical environment	SAFA-95	Problem to Solve Productivity

Short Name	Concept	User Need	Goal
			Organization --- Improve support of a task Provide comfortable and efficient working environment
Thank you	QR codes are added to the final product and customers are asked to say “thank you” to the Sunlight workers by executing the QR code. The “Thank you”-s are presented to the Sunlight workers. -> positive feedback. Customers can also be internal customers, i.e. departments that post-process parts from other departments can say thank you to the pre-processing department. Even more detailed individual workers can give “likes” to the work of co-workers.	SAFA-144 SAFA-145	Motivation Satisfaction --- Provide feeling of being valued Strengthen identification with work / product
Identify assembly parts	So far, when battery needs to be assembled, worker gets a list of articles to use, gets them in form of numbers, then he needs to manually compare the number to each of the articles in front of him. Solution: barcode scanner. Even better solution would be to get articles already in correct order	SAFA-176	Problem to Solve Productivity Organization --- Improve support of a task Provide comfortable and efficient working environment
Work schedule info screen	A screen at the workplace informs team about the current work schedule for the day, i.e. on which orders each member has to work	SAFA-152	Organization --- Support coordination of tasks Support autonomy at work Support transparency

4.4 FORTH MAJOR ITERATION

The forth major iteration consisted again of some concept refinements. Also further assessment aspects were added. Constraints is an assessment of technical and general obstacles. Generalizability was used to assess how easy it is to transfer the concept from Satisfactory to other factories. Finally, we checked for other limitations in the last column. The result is summarized in Table 9.

Table 9: Results of the forth major ideation iteration

Short Name	Concept	Constraints	Generalizability
Protect your Health	<p>Workers build teams and compete against other teams: who is the team with best wash hand scores.</p> <p>Daily / Weekly / Monthly basis?</p> <p>Hygiene Reports are generated.</p> <p>See Related Work section below the table.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Visualize the level of washed hands at door handles for own hall and other halls. -> create competition between halls. Trigger measurement once a day. Need to check how measurement is possible (sensors?).</p>	<p>no sensors?</p> <p>Moisture sensor?</p> <p>---</p> <p>privacy</p> <p>user identification</p> <p>technically not possible</p>	<p>with certain effort</p>
Quiz duel	<p>During breaks?</p> <p>The questions should not only be related to work!</p> <p>or slightly related: (Combining with Stories idea: "For which country these batteries are produced?")</p> <p>Motivation: everyone should get better at every time / personal evolvment</p> <p>Soccer quiz!</p> <p>---</p> <p>Dueled quiz is provided. Dedicated session after training for new employees. Alternative: Offer a dedicated session during work time, which people can enter voluntarily.</p> <p>Teams answer the questions as a team and play against another team. Rules like Quiz duel: One team selects a category and then answers 3 questions. Other team then has to answer the</p>	<p>depending on the level of detail may be difficult to implement</p> <p>---</p> <p>configurability</p>	<p>with certain effort</p>

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Short Name	Concept	Constraints	Generalizability
	<p>same questions and starts over with selecting a new category. Team with more correct answers wins after 6 rounds.</p> <p>The questions are connected to the work. This brings a training effect; workers learn while playing. The connection to the work is broad, for example, there can be questions about the boat for which the produced battery is used for. This increases the bond of worker and product/factory/company.</p> <p>Instead of textual questions, visual tasks that need to be solved in a group are provided. For example, assemble a battery. Next level: Assemble the boat for which the battery is used.</p>		
<p>Experience exchange platform instead of 4 (Help platform) and 5 (Knowledge platform)</p>	<p>Document best practices (e.g. SAFA-96) and get them rated,</p> <p>ask questions and receive answers and rate the answers (stack overflow),</p> <p>ask for help and look who needs help,</p> <p>request for training or offer training.</p> <p>Put screens on the doors (exits / lavatories / canteen / etc.) with last help and training requests.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Help platform:</p> <p>Platform where workers can provide trainings for work-related or not work-related issues. Maybe screens in every hall. Trainings can be asynchronous, like videos that can be requested when time and the provider does not need to be available at that time. Alternatively, live help can be requested which connects help provider with help requester.</p> <p>Knowledge platform:</p> <p>Platform where people can enter knowledge. Documented knowledge can be rated. Can be integrated in the help platform. Use tablet PC augmented reality platform.</p>		greatly
Jokes platform	<p>By providing means for communication, jokes will come automatically.</p> <p>Jokes should happen automatically, without enforcing them.</p>		greatly

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Short Name	Concept	Constraints	Generalizability
	<p>Thus, we decided not to consider this idea further.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Platform where jokes/links to funny content such as virals or interesting stories from the daily work can be uploaded. The content should increase satisfaction and team building first of all. Every week the funniest content of the week is awarded (the one with most clicks). -> positive feedback for the content provider. Then the other contents are erased. Always ordered by "last added" in order to have a fair rating mechanism</p> <p>Platform can be accessible inside factory (in areas where people pass by) in a public manner, e.g., public displays. This can enhance the work environment itself.</p>		
Suggestions for improvement	<p>Platform where workers can enter their suggestions for improvement (anonymously / they could put their name under, however, if they want).</p> <p>The suggestions should not be possible to be associate with the person.</p> <p>Wi-Fi Point in the canteen, then their mobile phones submit the anonymized suggestions.</p> <p>The suggestions can be viewed by all people working at the factory and rated / commented by them.</p> <p>Get feedback for these suggestions.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Platform makes sure that suggestion reaches the decider (How?). Decider has to enter whether it was applied, whether it was applied with modification or whether it was not applied. In the latter case, the reason for rejection is mandatory. This information is fed back to the worker who entered the suggestion.</p>		greatly
Food order	<p>Tool for managing collective orders at food delivery services. A worker initializes a collective order. For this, he chooses from a list of food delivery services in the city and sets the time for placing individual orders to 1 hour. All workers who have subscribed to be interested in</p>	<p>Food order services in Greece available?</p>	<p>hardly (if the food problem is not existing there is no sense of generalization)</p>

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Short Name	Concept	Constraints	Generalizability
	<p>collective food orders receive a notification at their smartphones. Then he places his own order, choosing from a list of available food from the selected delivery service. Using the system, workers can add their order to the collective order. They can browse the list of already ordered foods by their co-workers and “add one” (fast mode). Alternatively, they can select a food from the list provided by the selected delivery service. After the order time is run out, the possibility to add orders to the collective order is closed by the system and the collective order is transmitted to the delivery service</p>		
Story telling	<p>(Screens?) present information what a product is used for. The more details this story has, the more tangible it gets for the workers and they know why they are doing this work. For instance, the battery is used for a boat and the screen provides information about technical details of that boat, about the customer and for which purpose the boat is used.</p>	<p>Especially in the military sector there could be a problem with "officially" (i.e. over the platform) sharing details related to the customer and the usage of the product!!</p>	greatly
AR path	<p>Show path of material flow with AR glasses in shop floor mapped to the physical environment</p>		hardly
Thank you	<p>QR codes are added to the final product and customers are asked to say “thank you” to the Sunlight workers by executing the QR code. The “Thank you”-s are presented to the Sunlight workers. -> positive feedback. Customers can also be internal customers, i.e. departments that post-process parts from other departments can say thank you to the pre-processing department. Even more detailed individual workers can give “likes” to the work of co-workers.</p>		greatly
Identify assembly parts	<p>Currently, the operator responsible for the first step of the traction battery assembly process at Sunlight gets a printed list of articles. The articles in the list are represented by figures (numbers). The worker needs to manually compare the number in the list to each of the articles physically present on the shop floor until the</p>		with certain effort (how many facilities have the same problem in EU?)

Short Name	Concept	Constraints	Generalizability
	<p>particular article has been found.</p> <p>This procedure is quite tiresome and boring. It could be made more efficient and even maybe fun.</p> <p>Solution: barcode scanner. Even better solution would be to get articles already in correct order.</p>		
Work schedule info screen	A screen at the workplace informs team about the current work schedule for the day, i.e. on which orders each member has to work.		with certain effort (how many facilities have the same problem in EU?)
Idle Time	If idle time occurs, the worker can decide whether to help others or use the idle time, e.g. for surfing on the Internet.		greatly (with precaution of policies in other facilities)
Arcade game	Just put an arcade game outside, e.g. in the break/smoking area		greatly
Jokes Booth	A booth (or an area marked by other means) – which is characterized by the rule: when a person enters this area, they must tell a joke.		greatly

4.5 FIFTH MAJOR ITERATION

For the fifth major iteration, the goals that were introduced in the third iteration were analyzed with regard to their general background. So, the question to be answered was: What makes workers at a factory feel good? The answers could be categorized and associated to user needs (cf. Chapter 3), as Table 10 shows.

Table 10: Categorization of what makes workers at a factory feel good

What makes workers at a factory feel good?	Categories	User Need
carry responsibility	Being Valuable	
diversity at work	Not Boring, Exciting Tasks, Certain Complexity that Occupies the Mind	SAFA-149
good relationship with colleagues	Teamwork, Feel Right, Feel at Right Place	SAFA-151

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What makes workers at a factory feel good?	Categories	User Need
good mutual understanding and respect between the workers and their supervisors/bosses	Good Communication, Atmosphere, Teamwork	Culture, Good
being trusted (e.g. no unnecessary bureaucracy or questions coming from higher levels) / mutual trust	Good Trust, Good Atmosphere	Culture, Mutual
being familiar with the task or work environment / fit better into a role within a production (with accordance to skills)	Satisfaction, Feel Right, Feel at Right Place	Feel Familiar, Feel Comfortable, SAFA-154, 107, 93, 94
self-determination / autonomy at work	Satisfaction, Determination, Creativity	Self-SAFA-148, 101, 90
see own success and contribution to teamwork and even society (=> contribution on different levels: teamwork at a shop floor, collaboration between different divisions, usage of the products)	Motivation, Contribution, Useful and Valuable	Personal Being SAFA-175, 144, 145, 171
being able to identify themselves with the work they do and with the produced product (similar to the higher level of contribution; see above: contribution to the society)	Motivation, Identification with work/product	SAFA-170
guidance what to do in order to work better (not criticism, but friendly help!)	Teamwork, Communication, Better, Evolve	Training, Get (SAFA-96)
learn new things (personal development)	Training, Teamwork, Evolve	SAFA-155
helping others (generally at work or to learn new things)	Teamwork, Training, Being Useful	Being Valuable, SAFA-150, 100, 99
safe environment and co-workers that show (in their behavior) their awareness of safety issues	Safety	SAFA-87, 156, 93, 94
comfortable and efficient working environment	Organization, Satisfaction, No Problems	Productivity, SAFA-95, 3, 97, 98

In the fifth iteration, the concepts were once again refined. Afterwards, the “goal” column, introduced in the third iteration was replaced by a categories column according to Table 10. This and the formerly introduced assessment measures allowed deciding to pre-select concepts as follows.

4.5.1 **Selected concepts**

Table 11: Results of the fifth major ideation iteration, selected concepts

Short Name	Concept	Category
Idle Time	<p>Goal: Self-determined use of idle time w.r.t. competencies/skills, interests, or pleasure</p> <p>Idea: If idle time occurs, based on a provided estimation of its duration a worker can decide what to do:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • help others • build a two-person team with another worker according to their skills (e.g. English or welding) and interests (e.g. want to learn English or get better at welding) and train each other for these topics • take over some social tasks (e.g. make coffee) • or take idle time for yourself (e.g. for surfing on the Internet) <p>Concerns: Digitalizing of decisions and thus making them potentially transparent to the higher levels, can introduce certain pressure for decision-making process. A solution could be to reduce self-determination, but focus on strengthening the competency/skill and solidarity/help factors.</p>	<p>Satisfaction ---</p> <p>Self-determination Not getting bored Diversity at work Feel valued Strengthen/making use of competencies</p>
Arcade Game	<p>Goal: Increase the comfort and fun level of work environment</p> <p>Idea: Install an arcade game outside the shop floor, e.g. in the break/smoking area. Some arcade games could be soccer games!</p> <p>Concerns: Digital displays are not necessary relaxing for the eyes. For a good alternative, see idea 18 Kicker.</p>	<p>Satisfaction Self-determination</p>
The Product's Future	<p>Goal: To strengthen identification of workers with the product they produce</p> <p>Idea: For each product/order (or only for selected orders?) the worker can access interesting details about its future use. E.g. for motive power batteries there could be information on into what kind of vehicle they get embedded and how, how fast is this vehicle and how much energy is provided by the batteries at the maximum speed, who is the customer (if it is allowed to mention), etc. Alternatively, if it is a battery for a submarine, then technical details of that submarine (if it is not confidential) could be provided, and also information about the customer (if it is not confidential), who will be using the submarine and for which purpose (if it is also not confidential), etc.</p> <p>Notes: <i>Story Telling</i> (or <i>Tell Stories</i>) is a name that elicit associations to the notion of fiction and thus something not</p>	<p>Motivation ---</p> <p>Strengthen identification with work / product</p>

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Short Name	Concept	Category
	<p>necessary real. This is obviously not what we want. Thus, we definitely should find another name for this idea.</p> <p>I have started revising the name by proposing <i>The Product's Future</i> (or <i>The Product's Future Use</i>)</p> <p>Concerns: Especially in the military sector there could be a problem with "officially" (i.e. over the platform) sharing details related to the customer and the usage of the product!</p> <p>Sunlight already has this culture of "telling stories" and it obviously works well, thus an additional digital system will not necessarily bring a valuable benefit here. Therefore, we need to install this kind of system rather at Comau (if they do not have this kind of practice)!</p>	
Thank You!	<p>Goal: Communicate appreciation</p> <p>Idea: QR codes are added to the final product and customers are asked to say "thank you" to the Sunlight workers by executing the QR code. The "Thank you"-s are presented to the Sunlight workers. -> positive feedback. Customers can also be internal customers, i.e. departments that post-process parts from other departments can say thank you to the pre-processing department. Even more detailed individual workers can give "likes" to the work of co-workers.</p> <p>Concerns: The appreciation should be personal! Digitalism like QR-codes weakens the personal level of communication dramatically! Moreover, the current formulation of the idea introduces additional tasks for the customer! For a customer it is clear that they get a good product – they paid for that after all! It will be hard to communicate why a customer should do this additional step after delivery of the product, without introducing a risk of being misunderstood.</p> <p>Much more effective will be if a boss (director of a factory) with some regularity personally thanks the workers!!</p>	<p>Motivation</p> <p>Satisfaction</p> <p>---</p> <p>Provide feeling of being valued</p> <p>Strengthen identification with work / product</p>
Suggestions for Improvement	<p>Goal: Support and appreciate constructive criticism; provide workers with means for being able to evoke a change.</p> <p>Idea: Provide workers with means for submitting their suggestions for improvement anonymously.</p> <p>Thus, it should not be possible to associate the suggestions with a person!</p> <p>Establish a Wi-Fi access point in the canteen. Mobile phones that are connected to the access point automatically submit the anonymized suggestions that have been previously formulated and released for submission.</p> <p>Get feedback for submitted suggestions. (E.g. again by connecting to the same access point. Alternatively, a more</p>	<p>Satisfaction</p> <p>Organization</p> <p>Productivity</p> <p>Teamwork</p> <p>---</p> <p>Enhance self-determination</p> <p>Support / appreciate creativity</p>

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Short Name	Concept	Category
	<p>personal approach: In an open discussion (a meeting once a quarter) where the suggestions for improvement are presented and discussed.) In addition, a status of a submission could be available (e.g. submitted, in consideration, accepted, accepted with modifications, and rejected). For accepted submissions, the feedback can additionally contain information on the planned date of implementation. For rejected submissions, a reason should be clearly stated. For submissions that were accepted with modifications, the modifications shall be clearly stated.</p> <p>Note: The following part of the description has been deleted, because it could introduce bad dynamics in the factory:</p> <p>"The suggestions can be viewed by all people working at the factory and rated / commented by them."</p> <p>Concerns: Digital nature of submission could introduce trust issues related to anonymity (regardless the anonymity is actually provided by the system). Thus, analogue (or at least semi-analogue) submission should be considered as an alternative.</p>	
Experience Exchange Platform instead of 4 (Help platform) and 5 (Knowledge platform)	<p>Goal: Boost collaborative knowledge acquisition and exchange of best practices</p> <p>Idea: Provide a platform for the following activities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document best practices (e.g. SAFA-96) e.g. in form of videos, and get them rated, Ask questions and receive answers, and rate the answers (stack overflow), Ask for help and look who needs help (live help can be requested which connects help provider with help requester), Request for training or offer training. <p>Put screens on the doors (exits / lavatories / canteen / etc.) with last help and training requests.</p> <p>This idea can be connected with idea 11 Idle Time, with 17 Employees Open Profiles, and with 16 Wearable Pal.</p>	<p>Training Teamwork --- Provide help from colleagues on a personal level Create connection between co-workers Evoke feeling of being valuable and useful</p>
Protect your Health	<p>Goal: Motivate to wash hands</p> <p>Idea: Workers build teams and compete against other teams: whose team is with best scores for washing hands.</p> <p>Winner is calculated on Daily / Weekly / Monthly basis?</p> <p>Hygiene reports are generated.</p> <p>Related Work: http://www.biovigilsystems.com/biovigil-video/</p>	<p>Safety --- Healthcare Motivation to increase hygiene</p>

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Short Name	Concept	Category
	http://www.alibaba.com/showroom/ym--100a-portable-atp-bacteria-detection-meter.html	
Identify Assembly Parts	<p>Goal: Solve the following issue in the traction battery assembly department.</p> <p>Currently, the operator responsible for the first step of the traction battery assembly process at Sunlight gets a printed list of articles. The articles in the list are represented by figures (numbers). The worker needs to manually compare the number in the list to each of the articles physically present on the shop floor until the particular article has been found.</p> <p>This procedure is quite tiresome and boring. It could be made more efficient and even maybe fun.</p> <p>Idea: Provide a scanner for the labels of the assembly parts to compose a selected order. (Even better solution would be to get articles already in correct order.)</p> <p>A scanner can be a barcode scanner, or a OCR-A character scanner, e.g. integrated in the idea 16 Wearable Pal.</p>	<p>Problem to Solve</p> <p>Productivity</p> <p>Organization</p> <p>---</p> <p>Improve support of a task</p> <p>Provide comfortable and efficient working environment</p>

4.5.2 Unrated Promising concepts

During the fifth iteration, also some new ideas came up. They were seen as promising but did not go into the current selection because they did not undergo the same assessment cycle as the other ideas.

Table 12: Results of the fifth major ideation iteration, unrated promising concepts

Short Name	Concept	User Need	Category
Wearable Pal	<p>Goal: Provide cool and comfortable means for (self-determined) access of contextual information at the shop floor</p> <p>Idea: Wearable device showing contextual information to the worker wearing it. The information can be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • requests for training or help (see idea 4-5 Experience Exchange Platform) • alarm type and responsible person currently in the shift • current schedule data • »thank you« (see idea 10 Thank You!) <p>Moreover, wearable pal device could be used for the purposes of the following concepts as well:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 Protect your Health (SAFA-87) 	<p>SAFA-93</p> <p>SAFA-94</p> <p>SAFA-152</p> <p>SAFA-173</p> <p>SAFA-144</p> <p>SAFA-171</p>	<p>Organization</p> <p>Satisfaction</p> <p>Communication</p> <p>---</p> <p>UI for the different services (ideas)</p> <p>self-determination</p>

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Short Name	Concept	User Need	Category
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 11 identify assembly parts (SAFA-176) <p>Note: A wearable device can be e.g. a smart watch, smartphone, tablet PC or smart glasses (depending on the particular requirements at a workplace).</p>		
Open Profiles	<p>Goal: Support familiarity and relatedness between the employees</p> <p>Employees open profiles that contain the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Name Photo Skills (used in 4-5 Experience Exchange Platform to offer training and help) Currently at the factory? (yes/no) – possibly only for higher levels of employee hierarchy like employees in the HR department <p>The data is entered and its visibility is controlled by the respective employees themselves.</p>	<p>SAFA-151</p> <p>SAFA-150</p> <p>SAFA-174</p> <p>SAFA-107</p>	<p>Organization</p> <p>Teamwork</p> <p>---</p> <p>Self-determination</p>
Kicker	<p>Goal: Increase the comfort and fun level of work environment</p> <p>Idea: Install a kicker table outside the shop floor, e.g. in the break/smoking area (instead of the idea 14 Arcade Game).</p>	<p>SAFA-90</p> <p>Soccer games would refer to the most popular hobby (UX)</p>	<p>Organization</p> <p>---</p> <p>Feel comfortable</p>
Money Counter	<p>Goal: Increase motivation and boost teamwork feeling</p> <p>Idea: Display a "money counter" for the entire factory that for a particular amount of time (e.g. month) fills with "money" until a predefined target level has been reached. As soon as it has been reached, the "money" gets into the bonus cash box from which at the end of a period (e.g. 6 months) every employee gets a part.</p> <p>Note: I am currently not sure is it should be money or could be some metaphor.</p>		

4.5.3 Promising but Discarded for SatisFactory

One concept was considered as promising in general but not applicable for SatisFactory because the food delivery culture does not exist for the factories involved in SatisFactory.

Table 13: Results of the fifth major ideation iteration, promising but discarded concepts

Short Name	Concept	Category
Food order	Tool for managing collective orders at food delivery services. A worker initializes a collective order. For this, he chooses from a list of food delivery services in the city and sets the time for placing individual orders to 1 hour. All workers who have subscribed to be interested in collective food orders receive a notification at their smartphones. Then he places his own order, choosing from a list of available food from the selected delivery service. Using the system, workers can add their order to the collective order. They can browse the list of already ordered foods by their co-workers and “add one” (fast mode). Alternatively, they can select a food from the list provided by the selected delivery service. After the order time is run out, the possibility to add orders to the collective order is closed by the system and the collective order is transmitted to the delivery service	Organization Satisfaction --- Provide basic comfort

4.5.4 Second-Choice concepts

These are concepts that make sense and are promising; however, the other concepts were assessed to be more relevant for SatisFactory. Therefore, the ideas in Table 14 are something to be kept in mind.

Table 14: Results of the fifth major ideation iteration, second choice concepts

Short Name	Concept	Category
AR path	Show path of material flow with AR glasses in shop floor mapped to the physical environment	Problem to Solve Productivity Organization --- Improve support of a task Provide comfortable and efficient working environment
Work schedule info screen	A screen at the workplace informs team about the current work schedule for the day, i.e. on which orders each member has to work.	Organization --- Support coordination of tasks Support autonomy at work Support transparency

4.5.5 *Discarded*

After a careful consideration, these ideas have been estimated as not leading to a good solution and thus they have been discarded.

Table 15: Results of the fifth major ideation iteration, discarded concepts

Short Name	Concept	Category
Quiz duel	<p>During breaks?</p> <p>The questions should not only be related to work! or slightly related: (Combining with Stories idea: "For which country these batteries are produced?")</p> <p>Motivation: everyone should get better at every time / personal evolvment</p> <p>Soccer quiz!</p> <p>---</p> <p>Dueled quiz is provided. Dedicated session after training for new employees. Alternative: Offer a dedicated session during work time, which people can enter voluntarily.</p> <p>Teams answer the questions as a team and play against another team. Rules like Quiz duel: One team selects a category and then answers 3 questions. Other team then has to answer the same questions and starts over with selecting a new category. Team with more correct answers wins after 6 rounds.</p> <p>The questions are connected to the work. This brings a training effect; workers learn while playing. The connection to the work is broad, for example, there can be questions about the boat for which the produced battery is used for. This increases the bond of worker and product/factory/company.</p> <p>Instead of textual questions, visual tasks that need to be solved in a group are provided. For example, assemble a battery. Next level: Assemble the boat for which the battery is used.</p> <p>Concerning the technical feasibility, depending on the level of detail, it may be difficult to implement.</p>	<p>Training</p> <p>Teambuilding (when playing in teams)</p> <p>---</p> <p>Strengthen the bond between the workers and the product</p> <p>Promote a deeper understanding of work related topics</p> <p>(Provide an implicit technical training)</p>
Jokes platform	<p>By providing means for communication, jokes will come automatically.</p> <p>Jokes should happen automatically, without enforcing them.</p> <p>Thus, we decided not to consider this idea further.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Platform where jokes/links to funny content such as virals or interesting stories from the daily work can be uploaded. The content should increase satisfaction and team building first of all. Every week the funniest content of the week is awarded (the one with most</p>	<p>Teamwork / Teambuilding</p> <p>Communication Satisfaction</p> <p>---</p> <p>Cultivate good relationship with colleagues</p> <p>Have fun</p>

Short Name	Concept	Category
	<p>clicks). -> positive feedback for the content provider. Then the other contents are erased. Always ordered by "last added" in order to have a fair rating mechanism</p> <p>Platform can be accessible inside factory (in areas where people pass by) in a public manner, e.g., public displays. This can enhance the work environment itself.</p>	
Jokes Booth	<p>A booth (or an area marked by other means) – which is characterized by the rule: when a person enters this area, they must tell a joke.</p> <p>Jokes should happen automatically, without enforcing them.</p> <p>Thus, we decided not to consider this idea further.</p>	<p>Teamwork / Teambuilding</p> <p>Communication</p> <p>Satisfaction</p> <p>---</p> <p>Cultivate good relationship with colleagues</p> <p>Have fun</p>
Hall of Fame	<p>Critic: Personal feedback from a supervisor and most importantly the director of a factory is much more effective!</p> <p>It is a very hard problem to estimate an actual contribution of a person to a collaborative work, thus hall of fame will hardly be a good solution.</p>	<p>Satisfaction</p> <p>---</p> <p>Feel honored</p>

After finalizing the ideation process, the chosen concepts were presented to all other SatisFactory project partners. The whole consortium decided for which concepts to work further on. The details of this will be presented in Chapter 5.

5 DEVELOPED CONCEPTS FOR INCREASING ATTRACTIVENESS

This chapter reports on the concepts, which came out of the ideation process (cf. Chapter 4) and were selected to be elaborated on. Details about what was worked out are presented. Furthermore, the current state is described, i.e. why a concept was discontinued.

5.1 SUGGESTIONS PLATFORM

5.1.1 Use case description

Two iterations of use case descriptions were specified for the suggestions for improvement platform.

Table 16: Use Case description for Suggestions for improvement platform, first iteration

Use Case#	UC-5.1
Use Case Name	Platform for suggestions for improvement
Brief Description	<p>This UC is related to the operation of a web-based tool, where suggestions for improvement can be entered. The GUI is reduced to the minimum requested information and in general optimized with regard to usability so that suggestions can be entered quickly during short idle times. The tool is accessible from intra-factory Wi-Fi so that it is made sure that only factory workers can access it.</p> <p>The involved actors access the tool from their office workplace using an adapted interface. For each suggestion, they need to enter whether it was applied, whether it was applied with modification or whether it was not applied. In the latter case, the reason for rejection is mandatory. This information is fed back to the worker who entered the suggestion. The main flow of action is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of a potential for improvement • Provision of a suggestion • Deciding on a suggestion • Provision of feedback <p>A worker has an idea how to overcome a problem in the daily work process. It could also be that the worker firstly identified a problem and then also found a solution for it. He decides to make a suggestion for improvement.</p> <p>At a small idle time, the worker grabs his smartphone and browses to the suggestions for improvement platform. He quickly fills out the few mandatory forms in order to provide the suggestion to the platform.</p> <p>A manager opens the suggestions platform from his office computer and gets presented a list of suggestions that is relevant to him (we need to investigate how to find out for which decider a particular suggestion is relevant). At another idle time, the worker again logs in into the suggestions for improvement platform. He has a new notification telling him that his suggestion could not be applied due to the technical</p>

	<p>reasons.</p> <p>The system takes of anonymity and at the same time makes sure only factory employees can access it.</p>
Post-conditions	<p>Minimal Guarantees: Logging of suggestions for improvement</p> <p>Success Guarantees: A suggestion for improvement reaches the person who can decide on it. The worker gets feedback whether his suggestion was applied and, in case of rejection, the reason for the rejection.</p>
Goal (Successful End Condition)	<p>Improve the process of workers make suggestions for process improvements</p>
Use Case Initiation	<p>Worker identifies potential for improvement and decides to make a suggestion</p>
Involved Actors	<p>Supervisors, Operators & Technicians</p>

Table 17: Use Case description for Suggestions for improvement platform, second iteration

Use Case#	UC-5.1
Use Case Name	Platform for suggestions for improvement
Brief Description	<p>This UC is related to the operation of a web-based tool, where suggestions for improvement can be entered. The GUI is reduced to the minimum requested information and in general optimized with regard to usability so that suggestions can be entered quickly during short idle times. The tool is accessible from intra-factory Wi-Fi so that it is made sure that only factory workers can access it.</p> <p>The involved actors access the tool from their office workplace using an adapted interface. For each suggestion, they need to enter whether it was applied, whether it was applied with modification or whether it was not applied. In the latter case, the reason for rejection is mandatory. This information is fed back to the worker who entered the suggestion. The main flow of action is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of a potential for improvement • Provision of a suggestion • Deciding on a suggestion • Provision of feedback <p>A worker has an idea how to overcome a problem in the daily work process. It could also be that the worker firstly identified a problem and then also found a solution for it. He decides to make a suggestion for improvement.</p> <p>At a small idle time, the worker accesses the suggestions for improvement platform. Just a few taps and typing in his suggestion, would do the trick and his suggestion would reach the concerned party.</p> <p>Suggestions are allotted different categories in order to classify them in a more</p>

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	<p>meaningful and understandable manner. Each category has one or more allocated recipients. Only these recipients will receive the suggestions under that specific category.</p> <p>A worker may also view all the suggestions submitted to the platform. Additionally, he may also second someone else's suggestion in order to show his support for the idea. This would increase the overall awareness and would also act as a motivation factor for workers to put forward more suggestions.</p> <p>A manager opens the suggestions platform from his office computer and gets presented with a list of suggestions that are relevant to him. He may decide on those suggestions or request someone else to collaborate with him in order to take a more informed decision. At another idle time, the worker again logs into the suggestions for improvement platform. He has a new notification telling him that his suggestion could not be applied due to the technical reasons.</p> <p>The system takes care of anonymity and at the same time makes sure only factory employees can access it.</p>
Post-conditions	<p>Minimal Guarantees: Logging of suggestions for improvement</p> <p>Success Guarantees: A suggestion for improvement reaches the person who can decide on it. The worker gets feedback whether his suggestion was applied and, in case of rejection, the reason for the rejection.</p>
Goal (Successful End Condition)	Improve the process of workers making suggestions for process improvements
Use Case Initiation	Worker identifies potential for improvement and decides to make a suggestion
Involved Actors	Supervisors, Operators & Technicians

Use Case#	UC-5.1
Use Case Name	Platform for suggestions for improvement
Brief Description	<p>This UC is related to the operation of a web-based tool, where suggestions for improvement can be entered. The GUI is reduced to the minimum requested information and in general optimized with regard to usability so that suggestions can be entered quickly during short idle times. The tool is accessible from intra-factory Wi-Fi so that it is made sure that only factory workers can access it.</p> <p>The involved actors access the tool from their office workplace using an adapted interface. For each suggestion, they need to enter whether it was applied, whether it was applied with modification or whether it was not applied. In the latter case, the reason for rejection is mandatory. This information is fed back to the worker who entered the suggestion. The main flow of action is:</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of a potential for improvement • Provision of a suggestion • Deciding on a suggestion • Provision of feedback <p>A worker has an idea how to overcome a problem in the daily work process. It could also be that the worker firstly identified a problem and then also found a solution for it. He decides to make a suggestion for improvement.</p> <p>At a small idle time, the worker accesses the suggestions for improvement platform. Just a few taps and typing in his suggestion, would do the trick and his suggestion would reach the concerned party.</p> <p>Suggestions are allotted different categories in order to classify them in a more meaningful and understandable manner. Each category has one or more allocated recipients. Only these recipients will receive the suggestions under that specific category.</p> <p>A worker may also view all the suggestions submitted to the platform. Additionally, he may also second someone else's suggestion in order to show his support for the idea. This would increase the overall awareness and would also act as a motivation factor for workers to put forward more suggestions.</p> <p>A manager opens the suggestions platform from his office computer and gets presented with a list of suggestions that are relevant to him. He may decide on those suggestions or request someone else to collaborate with him in order to take a more informed decision. At another idle time, the worker again logs into the suggestions for improvement platform. He has a new notification telling him that his suggestion could not be applied due to the technical reasons.</p> <p>The system takes care of anonymity and at the same time makes sure only factory employees can access it.</p>
Post-conditions	<p>Minimal Guarantees: Logging of suggestions for improvement</p> <p>Success Guarantees: A suggestion for improvement reaches the person who can decide on it. The worker gets feedback whether his suggestion was applied and, in case of rejection, the reason for the rejection.</p>
Goal (Successful End Condition)	Improve the process of workers making suggestions for process improvements
Use Case Initiation	Worker identifies potential for improvement and decides to make a suggestion
Involved Actors	Supervisors, Operators & Technicians

Figure 10 shows the use case diagram.

Figure 10: Use Case diagram for suggestions for improvement

5.1.2 Stakeholder Interviews

Stakeholders from CERTH-CPERI, Sunlight and COMAU were interviewed for getting to know the environmental variables and constraints that are needed for designing the technology. Table 18 summarizes the insights.

Table 18: Stakeholder interviews regarding suggestions for improvement at the pilot plants

Questions	Answers		
	CERTH-CPERI	SUNLIGHT	COMAU
<p>When do workers have time to enter suggestions for improvement? (idle time?)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How long can idle times be for a worker? 	<p>We don't have any statistics on "idle time".</p> <p>Idle time is usually a joke here. 😊</p> <p>There are very short times between the tasks! The schedules are always full. Many of us even have lunch in front of our PCs, we cannot go somewhere, nor have a break of 30 minutes.</p> <p>There is actually nothing that can be designated as idle time.</p> <p>Although everyone has something to do all the time, filling in an online form should not be a problem. It is easy to find time for submitting a suggestion for improvements, since we are talking about 5 or 10 minutes. So, it should not be a problem for any of the</p>	<p>There is no idle time normally, only if something happens in the machinery.</p> <p>The workers come 20 minutes earlier before they reach the working positions.</p> <p>Usually idle times are breaks, or lunch times.</p> <p>If some issues occur with the production line: In most of the cases they will help repairing the machinery, they will not go anywhere, they remain in the working place and try to help somehow</p> <p>1 time per day in the production line, not in every production line</p> <p>the speed of solving the problem, fast: 30 minutes, is its more difficult than 3 hours usually 1-2 hours</p> <p>is the time being long, then the foreman</p>	<p>There is no waiting time. There are always some activities to do.</p> <p>Sometimes, when operators have finished their task, they go and talk to supervisors and get another task.</p> <p>Some operators, e.g. those working on an assembly line, have recurring activity and they have to do it all the time.</p> <p>Assembly process is organized in separate steps: assembly of the wrist, body, etc. Then there is a final assembly.</p> <p>If one component needs to be assembled, e.g. wrist, the worker needs to have the tools, such as screws and screwdriver, and the parts to be assembled.</p> <p>For the welding guns, there is one operator, who prepares trolleys that are carried from one assembly station to another. On each assembly</p>

Questions	Answers		
	CERTH-CPERI	SUNLIGHT	COMAU
	<p>involved actors. Especially when you give certain incentives like the feeling that this truly improves our work, as long it (the interface) is something simple!</p>	<p>will move them to another position</p> <p>in some cases, the worker may go for smoking and will have 5 minutes' break go for a drink to the canteen</p> <p>He cannot move from his position to other places for safety reasons</p> <p>In order to cook coffee, go for a cigarette he would need to clean hands, face, and maybe change cloths...</p> <p>During idle time the foreman decides what he should do, maybe cleaning, or help stacking batteries</p> <p>It depends.</p>	<p>station there is an operator positioned. There such steps as assembling of the body, the arms with electrodes, and then all the transformers are put together.</p> <p>Warehouse supplies the assembly lines with the parts.</p> <p>Depending on the assembled component, the parts are delivered. As mentioned before, for the welding guns there is a worker who prepares trolleys. There is no communication needed.</p> <p>There are several ways to do the assembly. All the steps are analyzed according to WCM, World Class Manufacturing Program (Toyota) - it stands for Sustainability, Ergonomics, Quality, etc.</p> <p>--</p> <p>What we can do for this platform for suggestions for improvements:</p> <p>We are thinking of improvement of a single robot assembly procedure. So, supporting operators during the assembly steps.</p> <p>E.g. we could provide some blank entry field, where an operator can input some notes like problems in the assembly, problems in the assembly procedures</p>

Questions	Answers		
	CERTH-CPERI	SUNLIGHT	COMAU
			The improvements should be done for the particular assembly process leading to continuous improvement , according to WCM.
<p>Do you have access to Internet at your factory?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who has access to it? (workers?) • How people access it? • What are the usage conditions? 	Yes. Everyone can access it.	Not allowed.	<p>Some of the factory's computers (like Pietro's), which have appropriate permissions, are able to access the Internet.</p> <p>Mobile phones are not allowed to access the intrafactory Internet.</p>
Do you have Intranet at your factory?	<p>There are several levels of intranet and internet.</p> <p>We are able to manage them as we need. Akis and Chrysa are the administrators.</p> <p>So, the infrastructure is there.</p> <p>Everyone can access it.</p> <p>The operators have PCs, for Satisfactory they maybe will need further HMIs (like GlassUP or Tablet</p>	<p>No intranet. Only LAN.</p> <p>The computers in the production line can access the LAN.</p>	<p>Yes.</p> <p>The workers on the shop floor cannot access it.</p> <p>The employee groups in the offices have access to it. E.g. those who work in the marketing, HR, engineering, or mechanical design departments. I.e. everyone who is not performing activities on the shop floor.</p>

Questions	Answers		
	CERTH-CPERI	SUNLIGHT	COMAU
	PCs)		
<p>Do you have intrafactory Wi-Fi?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who has access to it? • How people access it? • What are the usage conditions? • Is it administratively possible to ensure that only factory workers can get access to the Wi-Fi spot? 	<p>In the most of the places, there is Wi-Fi. Outside of the shop floor, there is sometimes a limited access, but there should be no problem.</p>	<p>For safety reasons Wi-Fi is not provided in the working area.</p> <p>There are some hotspots in the meeting rooms.</p> <p>Local Wi-Fi</p> <p>In the canteen, there are more than 100 people.</p>	<p>The complete factory is covered by Wi-Fi.</p> <p>All the company's computers have access to it.</p> <p>In order to make it accessible for workers it is possible to install some terminals, provided by Comau, at certain places in the factory accessible to workers. Alternatively, we can use the computers that we anyway plan to install for Satisfactory at operators' workplaces to support them with operation procedures.</p> <p>We can also experiment with Tablet PCs with the positivist perspective in the future, however, for Comau that employs more than 1000 people this solution is currently too expensive.</p>
<p>Do you deal with suggestions for improvement at your factory?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who submits these suggestions? 	<p>So far, we have only a system for laboratory analysis: coming from the auditors. ISO standards for chemical processes.</p> <p>We don't have anything at the shop floor.</p> <p>Actually when something safety</p>	<p>We receive suggestions from our workers.</p> <p>Currently suggestions are explained to foreman. The foreman communicates is with management, maintenance department.</p> <p>If a direct communication to foreman is not possible, then the worker writes the</p>	<p>Not aware of that.</p>

Questions	Answers		
	CERTH-CPERI	SUNLIGHT	COMAU
<p>(workers?)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How they submit the suggestions? Who is currently responsible for taking decisions whether suggestions for improvement will be implemented? How they currently decide on that / what is the current decision process? Are there multiple people who can be concerned with such decisions? 	<p>related happens, then the safety personnel makes a report including such reports.</p> <p>No particular information related to the shop floor.</p> <p>The suggestions for improvement are on the informal basis. (no formal things)</p> <p>If an operator has some ideas, he talks with other operators and discuss. Usually it happens orally.</p> <p>Depending on the topic, there are different decision-makers: maintenance team, managers, director, etc.</p> <p>There are e.g. the categories like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Group of plants Safety Maintenance Calibration Building <p>CHRYSA WILL SEND the categories and the roles of people / examples of</p>	<p>suggestion on a piece of paper and submits it to production line supervisor. On some position</p> <p>There is actually no a common way for submission of suggestion.</p> <p>It can be applied to Sunlight.</p> <p>This would be a good idea for SF to implement.</p> <p>The problem is that currently the worker doesn't know what happens with their suggestion. It would be a good idea to have a suggestion status in a week.</p> <p>In most cases, the foreman must communicate to higher levels to be able to trigger a decision.</p> <p>Decision-makers: depends on the suggestion. If it is about the product, then product development. If it is about the production process: production line supervisor, the director, maintenance supervisor, foremen. Have a meeting.</p> <p>Product development, maintenance, and top management, e.g. production line supervisor</p>	

Questions	Answers		
	CERTH-CPERI	SUNLIGHT	COMAU
<p>Is from the company's perspective a (financial) reward for the best improvement thinkable?</p>	<p>people responsible for decisions.</p> <p>When some operator observes that something doesn't work optimal, We don't have some ideas about that. It is hard to compare the suggestions.</p> <p>The best reward is that suggestions actually get implemented, and contribute to the improvement of our work.</p> <p>Money is not possible as a reward.</p> <p>Otherwise, we are open for ideas of rewarding.</p>	<p>SYMEON SENDS: a table categorization of decision-makers</p> <p>The opinion of foreman is critical, the opinion of production supervisor is also critical</p> <p>yes, why not</p> <p>I cannot think about a way this moment</p>	<p>At Comau, we don't have rewards for improvements.</p> <p>However, at Fiat there are prizes for best idea! (according to WCM and continuous improvement)</p>
<p>Do you have a database / directory with all the e-mail addresses and mobile phones of the workers?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the data complete? 	<p>see below</p>	<p>They don't have company e-mail addresses.</p> <p>Suggestion: possibility for registration</p>	<p>No such directory for workers yet.</p>

Questions	Answers		
	CERTH-CPERI	SUNLIGHT	COMAU
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is it theoretically possible to use the data for suggestions for improvement platform for notification purposes? (e.g. with special agreement of the workers?) 			
<p>Do you have a database / directory with all the e-mail addresses and mobile phones of the deciders?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the data complete? Is it theoretically possible to use the data for suggestions for improvement platform for notification 	<p>There is an e-mail database of the accounts.</p> <p>Existing mailing lists: process, technical team, all together</p> <p>It is possible to create appropriate mailing lists for the suggestions platform.</p>	<p>Not known.</p> <p>Mailing list can be established.</p> <p>Currently there is no repository with updated e-mails. Solved forwarding.</p> <p>We are open to suggestion.</p>	<p>Yes, for employees working in the offices the e-mails are kept up to date by using the Microsoft Exchange format.</p> <p>Employees of the Fiat Group use Outlook.</p> <p>Microsoft Exchange and Microsoft Lync (kind of Skype) are used.</p>

Questions	Answers		
	CERTH-CPERI	SUNLIGHT	COMAU
purposes? (e.g. with special agreement of the deciders?)			
How workers identify themselves at your factory? (swipe cards?)	<p>Personal swipe cards to enter the building, but it is not mandatory to use them.</p> <p>If someone doesn't come to the institute because of illness, then the person needs to inform the supervisor.</p>	<p>ID cards</p> <p>Magnetic cards, they use in the special identification positions around the facility</p>	<p>Everyone uses a badge equipped with a magnetic band and RFID</p>

5.1.3 *Functional scope*

The functionalities of the suggestions for improvement platform vary for different users. The following user groups were identified:

- **Simple users:** Can be workers or managers
- **Decision-makers:** Managers with the power of accepting/declining suggestions in a specific category
- **Administrators:** Managers with the power of deleting and editing suggestions and user information.

The functionalities for the user groups are as follows. Key features for each user group are bold. All functionalities available to simple users will be available to decision-makers/managers. Administrators will have full access to all functionalities.

Simple users

- **Submit suggestion**
- **View all suggestions**
- **View suggestion details**
- Up/down vote suggestion
- Search for suggestions
- Filter suggestions

Decision makers

- **Login/Logout**
- **Change suggestion status (accept, accept with modifications, reject)**
- **View suggestions addressed to me (filter)**
- Invite collaborator
- View all collaboration invites
- View collaboration invite details
- Accept/decline collaboration invite
- Add decision maker from committee to suggestion (as member)
- Remove decision maker from committee from suggestion (as member)

Administrators

- **Delete suggestion**
- **Add/edit/delete decision-maker account**
- Add/edit/delete decision-maker committee
- Add/edit/delete category (will not be implemented, but is listed for sake of completeness)

5.2 **SOCIAL INTERACTION PLATFORM**

5.2.1 **Use case description**

According to “Supporting Collaboration Processes” described in 2.3 of the current document, the tools needed for the social collaboration platform are presented shortly in this chapter, with their functionalities, actors and use cases.

5.2.1.1 **Collaborative Use Cases**

UC – 2 Learning environment with interactive activities for multipurpose operations	Sub - Use case 2.1 In-factory training and support of workers using a flexible learning platform.	Sub - Use Case 2.1.1: UC – 2.1.1 Support each other
UC-4 Intelligent decision support and maintenance for increased flexibility	Sub – Use Case 4.2 Acquire work schedule and sequence of actions	Sub – Use Case 4.2.1 UC – 4.2.1 Schedule Support
UC-5 Collaboration and Social interaction for increased workers’ engagement	Sub – Use Case 5.1 Gamification Framework	Sub – Use Case 5.1.1 UC – 5.1.1 Manage Gamification
	Sub – Use Case 5.3 Gamified platform for suggestions for improvement	Sub – Use Case 5.3.1 UC – 5.3.1 Access suggestion tool
	Sub – Use Case 5.4 Instantiation of gamification framework	Sub – Use Case 5.4.1 UC – 5.4.1 Gamification Information
UC-6 Presentation of activities and bidirectional communication for	Sub – Use Case 6.3 Knowledge sharing among workers based on advanced reasoning	Sub - Use Case 6.3.1: UC – 6.3.1 Share knowledge

enhanced shop floor
feedback

Figure 11: Collaboration Use Cases

UC – 2.1.1 Support each other

Use Case ID	UC-2.1.1
Use Case Name	Support each other
Version/Author	v1/CERTH/ITI
Brief Description	The social collaboration platform will provide the possibility to the users to connect with each other and ask or seek for help when needed. Additionally, they can support each other through a support-oriented environment where questions can be asked and answers can be given by the users (Tips & Tricks tool).
Assumptions or Pre-conditions	In order to use the social platform users should create an account. Users have access to the tips & tricks tool through the social platform – networking is vital for this forum-like platform.
Post - conditions	Users receive awards according to their actions.
Goal (Successful End Condition)	Users have received successfully the support they needed directly through communication in social platform or through tips & tricks tool in the platform. Novice workers have received support by the experienced, reducing stress, enhancing cooperation, avoiding mistakes in a safe support-oriented environment.
Involved Actors	Supervisor, Operators & technicians
Use Case Initiation	Users can start support each other by login to the satisfactory platform. Through the interface they have access to communication and tips & tricks tools.
Architecture Components Involved	
Related Business Scenario	BSC1.1, BSC1.2, BSC2.1, BSC4.1, BSC4.3
Relationship with other Use Cases	UC-5.1.1, UC-5.4.1, UC-6.3.1
Addressed requirements of the system	
Restrictions	

Figure 12: Support each other

UC – 4.2.2 Schedule Support

Use Case ID	UC-4.2.1
Use Case Name	Schedule Support
Version/Author	v1/CERTH/ITI
Brief Description	Users can be informed about schedule changes through social collaboration platform. The empowered employee have the possibility to publish it and other workers can receive notification for changes.
Assumptions or Pre-conditions	The empowered employee can post in the whole network or in specific co-workers in private or in public mode.
Post - conditions	Users receive awards according to their actions.
Goal (Successful End Condition)	Users have informed co-workers about schedule changes synchronously or asynchronously, public or private avoiding confusions, reducing stress.
Involved Actors	Supervisor, Operators & technicians
Use Case Initiation	Users can share or be notified about a schedule change after login.

Architecture Components Involved	
Related Business Scenario	BSC1.1, BSC1.2, BSC2.1, BSC3.1, BSC4.1, BSC4.2, BSC4.3, BSC5.1, BSC5.2, BSC5.3
Relationship with other Use Cases	
Addressed requirements of the system	
Restrictions	

Figure 13: Schedule Support

UC – 5.4.1 Gamification Information

Use Case ID	UC-5.4.1
Use Case Name	Gamification Information
Version/Author	v1/CERTH/ITI
Brief Description	<p>Workers can be informed about their gamified actions, games that they participate or have completed, awards such as badges, achievements, points earned. They can view their place in leaderboards in each game they participate and in total. Their progress is also visible through levels and points needed for next level.</p> <p>Each user has each own summary achievement page which is open and visible by others, and supervisors.</p> <p>Through notifications workers can be informed when a new game is available or a new member entered a team, as well as the awards they receive using the platform.</p> <p>Supervisors are notified for workers participation in games and other important facts in gamified platform.</p>
Assumptions or Pre-conditions	In order for the users to view their own achievements login is necessary. Every user can view others users' profiles.
Post - conditions	Users receive awards according to their actions.
Goal (Successful End Condition)	Knowing progress, achievements and personal skills and records is enhancing personal motivation and self-esteem accompanied by good feelings about work and satisfaction.
Involved Actors	Supervisor, Operators & technicians
Use Case Initiation	Login is necessary.
Architecture Components Involved	
Related Business Scenario	BSC4.3, BSC5.3
Relationship with other Use Cases	UC – 2.1.1, UC – 5.1.1, UC – 5.3.1, UC – 6.3.1
Addressed requirements of the system	
Restrictions	

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Figure 14: Gamification Information

UC – 6.3.1 Share Knowledge

Use Case ID	UC-6.3.1
Use Case Name	Share Knowledge
Version/Author	v1/CERTH/ITI
Brief Description	Workers and supervisors can share knowledge through social network tools and tips & tricks platform.
Assumptions or Pre-conditions	Users have to be connected to the platform in order to communicate and exchange experience and knowledge.
Post - conditions	Users receive awards according to their actions.
Goal (Successful End Condition)	Receiving and providing support is essential for on work collaboration. Novice workers receive support in a support-oriented environment and can reach a level of skills which they could not reach without their experienced co-workers. Experienced workers share their knowledge and feel much more useful and satisfied.
Involved Actors	Supervisor, Operators & technicians
Use Case Initiation	Login and use of tips & tricks tool or communication tools in the social platform.

Architecture Components Involved	Tips & tricks, communication tool
Related Business Scenario	BSC1.1, BSC1.2, BSC2.1, BSC3.1, BSC4.1, BSC4.2, BSC4.3, BSC5.1, BSC5.2, BSC5.3
Relationship with other Use Cases	UC – 2.1.1, UC – 5.1.1, UC – 5.4.1
Addressed requirements of the system	
Restrictions	

Figure 15: Share Knowledge

5.2.1.2 **Collaborative Tools**

1. Communication tool (social network-like platform)

Operators & technicians

- View available games (title, description, tasks, awards, priority)
- Create teams
- Search Tool for activities, videos and users
- Participate in game (individual, team)
- Profile:
 - Status (total points, level)
 - Awards earned

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-Completed games (title, description, tasks, awards, priority, leaderboards)

Supervisor, Operators & technicians

- Post text/video/photo on public or private
- Messenger text/video/photo to a single person/team
- Search Tool for activities, videos and users
- UI use for medium/large screens
- Multimedia content access
- Notifications for schedule changes
- Notifications for gamified processes
- User settings for account, privacy and notifications
- File attachment in platforms messenger

2. Tips & Tricks tool (Questions & Answers tool)

Supervisor, Operators & technicians

- Ask a question
- Answer a question
- Comment an answer
- Vote
- Documentation
- Editor for video, image, text
- Tags and Categories
- Search engine
- Date and time
- Training Apps reminder
- File attachments
- Multimedia files are viewable

5.2.2 **Goals**

Main Goals of Social Collaboration Platform arising from user and social gamification requirements are:

- Users' motivation and engagement enhancement
- Gamification processes construction
- Communication and collaboration
- Satisfaction for individuals and teams
- Exchange knowledge and experience
- Participants' Notification for incidents, schedule changes, gamification and social actions
- Access in question & answers tools

Social Collaboration Platform aims to provide a rich multitask environment where all of the workers can communicate with each other regardless of their physical or work position. Collaboration and motivation of workers is reinforced by gamification mechanisms possible to be implemented in all of the platform procedures by the supervisor.

Effective networking at work is an other major goal of the social collaboration platform, with which not only new recruits but also experienced workers can benefit. Connection between co-workers from the same or different departments or between current, previous and upcoming workers strengthens the teamwork and collaboration. Users can form the content of the social platform not only with work issues but also off – work discussions and posts having fun during work. Sharing new ideas is also essential for factories that need to be innovated. Social platform provides the space where these new ideas can be discussed synchronously and asynchronously with few or many participants from different disciplines with the possibility to generate innovative schemata.

With every process being gamified there are a lot of opportunities for employees to discover and practice their skills. Implemented in the social platform these activities can be promoted and advertised in and out of the factory.

Gamification elements such as leaderboards enhance users’ engagement while when they view themselves in the crowd they feel motivated to continue trying to reach a next level of skill or experience. Information about the progress of user in a game, the level of experience, the awards earned are powerful gamification elements that reinforce users’ satisfaction in workplace while they feel that their actions matter, are recognized and awarded. As a consequence, they feel satisfaction at work and they are more collaborative, effective, productive and happy.

Exchange of knowledge and experience enhances teamwork as well. Experienced workers feel good sharing information and best practices while new recruits feel safe asking for information and solutions through an attractive and support-oriented environment.

Social collaboration platform, through the human-oriented design approach, aims to give the tools to the users to grow individually and in teams, promoting self-esteem and team bonds by the awards and voting systems. Awards indicate the experts, and the well-practiced workers but also the workers that participate and learn new things. Voting system facilitates the quality of questions and answers in tips & tricks tools and liking system enhance users’ participation and sharing in network.

5.3 PRODUCTS FUTURE

5.3.1 Use case description

Table 19 shows how the “product’s future” concept was integrated in BSC-4.1. The particular parts for this concept are underlined.

Table 19: The product's future concept integrated in BSC-4.1

Application Scenario #	BSC- 4.1
Application Scenario Name	Motive power battery assembly line
Goal	Improve the working environment in motive power batteries assembly line
Challenges	The challenge is to provide in each assembly stage all the necessary technical information to the actors in a ‘smart’ way. Reduce confusion and misinterpretation of request job

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	Identification of the respective physical world objects that are mentioned in the descriptions. <u>Create a better bond of workers with the product. Strengthen identification with work / product. See that you contribute to a greater goal. Feel proud or valuable.</u>
Involved Actors	Production supervisor, Workers, Foreman
Post-conditions (Minimal Guarantees, Success Guarantees)	Minimal Guarantees: Assembly motive power batteries Success Guarantees: Assembly motive power batteries retrieving all the necessary technical information from an information system through a context aware tablet or computer. <u>Workers have knowledge what the product is used for and are proud of it.</u>
Realization Concept	The system should provide information about the motive power battery assembly line such as customer order details, mechanical drawings, connections diagrams, assembly instructions, inspection instructions, packing instructions. All this information would be easy accessible from the actors and would be displayed in tablets or wall screens located in the shop floor. The system will display the Work Order will be executed next, recognize the type of battery and provide the relevant information on the screens. The screen information can be easily matched to physical world objects through a barcode scanner. <u>Screens present information what the battery is used for. The more details this story has, the more tangible it gets for the workers and they know why they are doing this work. For instance, the battery is used for a boat and the screen provides information about technical details of that boat, about the customer and for which purpose the boat is used.</u>

5.3.2 Stakeholder Interviews

Stakeholders from CERTH-CPERI, Sunlight and COMAU were interviewed for getting to know the environmental variables and constraints that are needed for designing the technology. Table 20 summarizes the insights.

Table 20: Stakeholder interviews regarding the product's future at the pilot plants

Question	Answer		
	CERTH	SUNLIGHT	COMAU
Do the industrial sites (CERTH and Comau) tell their workers about the future use of the products?	No. This kind of information is not given to the process operators. There is no need to know for the technical team. Along with industrial projects, there are also research projects we	It is strange for the mentality of the company. They are giving press releases, announcement boards at SUNLIGHT.	The operators know who the customer is. Daimler, Fiat, etc. have different standards, the operators need to comply with these standards and,

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Question	Answer		
	CERTH	SUNLIGHT	COMAU
	are concerned with, which do not have any clients.		thus, they know who the customer is.
Is such information about the future use of a product allowed to present to the workers?	Yes, they anyway can see on the materials they use who is the customer. The materials are tagged with the customer/client information.	This kind of information is already released at the website.	Yes
According to the official agreements, how confidentially this information about the customers and their orders is?	It is not confidential.	In most cases, the workers do not know who the customer is, because the customers do not want it. (One example was that there are some companies, for which Sunlight produces the batteries, distribute the batteries under their own brand. And transparency in this regard, according to the contract between these companies and Sunlight, is not wanted.)	s. above

After performing these steps, the pilot stakeholders decided that this idea is not relevant for them. So, it was not developed further. Instead, focus was put on the other concepts.

5.4 BATTERY ASSEMBLY PRACTICE SUPPORT

This idea supports a concrete day-to-day problem, which was identified at Sunlight. As first step, the current process and the process, which is improved by our idea, was depicted by storyboards in order to convey the concept.

5.4.1 Storyboards

The storyboard in Figure 16 shows the current process of assembling batteries.

Figure 16: Current battery assembly process

A worker has to get assembly parts from a storeroom. The parts are stored in boxes, which are placed in the room in an unordered way. Each box has a label with an identification number. The worker got an order list on a piece of paper with identification numbers, which he has to manually compare to the numbers on the boxes. When he found the correct box, he brings it to the assembly area and starts assembling the battery.

The manual comparison is the suboptimal part of this process, especially because the boxes are unordered. It is time-consuming, error-prone, tiresome and boring for the worker.

Figure 17 shows how we planned to improve the process.

Figure 17: Improved battery assembly process

Simple displays are introduced to the storeroom’s walls, which can display order numbers. On top of each display, there is a light, which can be switched on and off. When placing the boxes to the storeroom, the worker makes sure to place the boxes to the correct order numbers. The order list is now transmitted to the worker, who is going to assemble a battery, by a tablet computer, which is fixed to his forklift. When clicking a particular number, the respective number on top of the display is switched on. This way, the worker knows which box to get.

The rest of the process stays the same. The worker brings the box to the assembly area and starts assembling the battery.

The idea was discussed in a plenary meeting. It was assessed as valid concept but in the end, it was decided to go with the other concepts and not implement this one.

5.5 **PROTECT YOUR HEALTH**

5.5.1 **Use case description**

Table 21 shows how the “Protect your Health” concept was integrated in UC-5.

Table 21: Use Case description for Protect your Health concept

Use Case#	UC-5
Use Case Name	Protect your Health
Brief Description	<p>This UC is related to formulating a system that motivates the workers to wash their hands regularly, especially before they are going to eat something. This ensures their safety by making sure that they will not eat anything with their lead-infected hands. The system does this by introducing gamification, which adds to the motivation of the workers to keep their hands washed and clean at all times.</p> <p>Upon detection of unwashed, lead-infected hands, the worker washes his hands and earns points for cleanliness. These points are added to the aggregate score of</p>

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	his team. Different teams of workers compete with each other and the team with maximum cleanliness points wins.
Post-conditions	Minimal Guarantees: Identification of unwashed hands Success Guarantees: Worker washes hands if unwashed hands are identified and in doing so, earns scores to ensure that his team wins
Goal (Successful End Condition)	Motivate worker to wash hands by introducing a sense of competition among different teams in order to ensure safety of the workers
Use Case Initiation	Worker gets tested for cleanliness
Involved Actors	Operators & Technicians

Figure 18: Use case diagram for Protect your Health

5.5.2 Storyboards

The storyboard in Figure 19 depicts the use case described in Section 5.5.1. A smart handle at the canteen door detects when a worker has lead on his hands and notifies the worker by signaling red. After having cleaned his hands from lead, the handle detects this, signals green and the worker gets 2 points. Each worker is associated to a team and the team points are visualized at a public display.

Figure 19: Storyboard for Protect your Health concept, first iteration

After an assessment with stakeholder from Sunlight, two major problems with the concept were identified. One problem is the technical feasibility. Additional and complicated hardware installations would be needed and it was not clear if the required sensor technology would exist at all. The second problem is the public exposure of the team points. This implicitly exposes one team as loser team, even more, as dirty team. This can cause social problems and has to be avoided.

In order to overcome these problems, the concept was adjusted as Figure 20 shows.

Figure 20: Storyboard for Protect your Health concept, second iteration

Instead of letting teams compete with each other, there is only one team, which competes to its own result of the former day. The goal for every day is to be better than the day before. If at the end of the day, the former day score was beaten, the today's score become the score to beat for the next day. If it was not beaten, the score to beat is reset. This is called win streak approach.

Besides not having to expose one team as loser and dirty team, technical feasibility is much better because no complicated lead sensors need to be designed. Instead, it is possible to equip soap dispensers in the bathrooms so that they detect if soap was pulled.

5.5.3 *Functional scope*

A soap dispenser is equipped with hardware, which detects when soap was pulled. Then, it sends this information wirelessly to the gamification framework (cf. Section 5.6). The system makes sure that, e.g., when a worker pulls soap 3 times in a short range this is counted only once for the gamification.

5.6 **GAMIFICATION FRAMEWORK**

5.6.1 *Use case description*

This list of Use Cases targets mostly to apply the various concepts of gamification in the factory. Figure 21 shows the analysis of UC-5. In this section we shall go into the details of UC-5.1 regarding the Gamification Framework, UC-5.3 regarding the gamified platform for suggestions for improvement and UC-5.4 regarding the instantiation of the gamification framework. UC-5.2 regarding the details of the platform for suggestions for improvement has been explain in section 5.1.

Figure 21 Analysis of UC-5

At the following table there is an analysis of the Use Case 5.1 regarding the gamification framework.

Table 22 UC-5.1 Gamification framework

Use Case #	UC-5.1
Use Case Name	Gamification framework
Brief Description	<p>The Gamification Framework is a framework for applying gamification in various aspects of SatisFactory. Different external systems can use the APIs provided by this framework to become a part of the whole gamification environment at the factory.</p> <p>Each game is created by either the external systems or the management. Each game can consist of various tasks. Each task is of certain points. Workers can take part in this game either individually or in the form of teams. Upon performing a specific task, the external system informs the Gamification Framework about the worker who performed the task and the task he just performed. That worker or his team, depending on the game type, is awarded with the respective points. These points are then accumulated into a grand total which shows whether the workers have surpassed their previous score or not. The collective information is displayed on the Digital Display Screen. The workers can also view their personal scores and achievements via a mobile app.</p>

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Pre-conditions	The SatisFactory Applications are integrated to the Gamification framework
Post-conditions	All Applications contribute to the overall scoring for every participant based on the applications rules
Goal (Successful End Condition)	Gamification motivate users to perform better in the domain of every SatisFactory Application
Use Case Initiation	An application initiates connection with the framework
Involved Actors	Supervisors, Operators & Technicians
Architecture Components Involved	SatisFactory Repository, Collaborative Tools
Related Business Scenario	BSC1, BSC2, BSC3, BSC4, BSC5
Relationship with other Use Cases	UC-5
Addressed requirements of the system	SAFA IDs: 221, 220, 218, 217, 215, 206, 205, 204, 174, 131, 120, 62, 59
Restrictions	Safety: All actors involved in the use case should be compliant with the safety requirements and the instructions given by the safety manager.

Figure 22 Analysis of UC-5.1

Table 23 explains the analysis of the Use Case 5.3 regarding the gamified platform for suggestions for improvement.

Table 23 UC-5.3 Gamified Platform for suggestions for improvement

Use Case #	UC-5.3
Use Case Name	Gamified Platform for suggestions for improvement
Brief Description	<p>This UC extend UC5.2 by introducing gamification for motivating users.</p> <p>In the suggestions for improvement system, workers submit suggestions for process or other improvements over an electronic system to deciders. All submitted suggestions can be watched and voted in an anonymous way.</p> <p>The workers can collect points for the same gamification framework instance using the suggestions for improvement platform. That means they get a certain amount of points for each task they perform using this platform.</p>
Pre-conditions	Not Applicable
Post-conditions	<p>Minimal Guarantees: Logging of suggestions for improvement</p> <p>Success Guarantees: A suggestion for improvement reaches the person who can decide on it. The worker gets feedback whether his suggestion was applied and, in case of rejection, the reason for the rejection.</p>
Goal (Successful End Condition)	Improve the process of workers make suggestions for process improvements
Use Case Initiation	Worker identifies potential for improvement and decides to make a suggestion
Involved Actors	Supervisors, Operators & Technicians
Architecture Components Involved	Visualization toolkit, Collaborative Tools, Gamification Framework, Middleware
Related Business Scenario	BSC-1, BSC-3.1
Relationship with other Use Cases	UC-5.1, UC-5.3
Addressed requirements of the system	SAFA IDs: 143, 41
Restrictions	-

Figure 23 presents the connection of the Use case with the SatisFactory.

Figure 23: Analysis of UC-5.3

Table 24 explains the analysis of the Use Case 5.4 regarding the instantiation of the gamification framework.

Table 24: UC-5.4 Instantiation of Gamification Framework

Use Case #	UC-5.4
Use Case Name	Instantiation of Gamification Framework
Brief Description	This UC is related to formulating a system that motivates the workers to engage at the instantiation of the Gamification Framework regularly. The system does this through gamification which increases the motivation of the workers to keep up their engagement with the Gamified Framework. Upon detection of actor’s engagement, the system records the respective actions / feedback and the actor earns points. These points are added to the aggregated score of her global team that always compete against their own best day score.
Pre-conditions	Worker identification at the system where the instantiation of Gamification Framework is deployed
Post-conditions	The worker has earned points according to the Gamification process he followed
Goal (Successful End Condition)	Motivate worker to engage at the instantiated game in order to improve work satisfaction
Use Case Initiation	Worker uses the instantiation of the Gamification Framework
Involved Actors	Supervisors, Operators & Technicians

Architecture Components Involved	Collaborative Tools, Gamification Framework, Visualization toolkit
Related Business Scenario	BSC-4.3, BSC-5.3
Relationship with other Use Cases	UC-5.2
Addressed requirements of the system	SAFA IDs: 220, 215, 205, 146, 136, 105, 41, 17, 4
Restrictions	-

Figure 24 present the connection of the Use case with the SatisFactory components.

Figure 24 Analysis of UC-5.4

5.6.2 Goals

The main goal of introducing the concept of gamification to SatisFactory is to increase the worker's satisfaction at work. The idea is to have a central gamification framework. Various Satisfactory components can communicate with this central framework to be a part of the whole gamified environment. The goal is to motivate the user by invoking a sense of gamification to his daily routine tasks.

5.6.3 Functional scope

The gamification framework provides various Satisfactory components with an interface with which they can interact and submit points. These points are assigned to different tasks the workers can perform using the gamified Satisfactory components. The gamification framework is also responsible for keeping a track of all the games created by each component. It uses the Digital Andon System to display the accumulative score of the workers for all the gamified components. Moreover, it uses the social collaboration platform to display the individual points of the worker for each gamified component separately.

5.6.4 Usage scenarios

Figure 25 shows the relationship of UC-5.1 regarding the gamification framework with other use cases and business scenarios.

Figure 25 Relationship of UC-5.1 with other UCs and BSCs

Figure 26 shows the relationship of UC-5.3 regarding the gamified platform for suggestions for improvement, with other use cases and business scenarios.

Figure 26 Relationship of UC-5.3 with other UCs and BSCs

Figure 27 shows the relationship of UC-5.4 regarding the instantiation of the gamification framework, with other use cases and business scenarios.

Figure 27 Relationship of UC-5.4 with other UCs and BSCs

5.6.5 Connection with Gamified Components

Table 25 shows various tasks that contribute to the gamification in terms of points. These tasks belong to different SatisFactory components, that the workers can perform while interacting with these systems.

Table 25 : Gamified tasks of various SatisFactory components

System	Gamified Action
Suggestions for Improvement	Submit a suggestion
	Submitted suggestion gets accepted
	Up voting a suggestion
Protect your Health	Wash Hands
Gesture & Content Recognition	Safety equipment correctly worn before entering the smart assembly station
	Assembly operation performed without modifications after the checklist validation
Maintenance	Update already existing instructions
	Enrich already available information by uploading a photo attachment that showcases the problem and/or solution
Training	Experienced worker helps novice, trigger by trainee
	Experienced worker helps novice, trigger by novice worker who asked for the specific guru
	Experienced worker helps novice, trigger by himself/herself
	Novice worker completes training, trigger by supervisor or experienced worker

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	Novice worker completes training, trigger by himself/herself
Social Collaboration Platform	Post a question in the forum
	Answer a question in the forum
	Upvote or downvote a question/answer in the forum

5.6.6 *Connection to Digital Andon*

The digital andon system described in Chapter 6 is used as a visual output for the team points. The visual design of this is described in Section 4.2 of Deliverable D3.2 - Situated and Attractive Information Exchange Techniques for Workers. The corresponding implementation details, i.e. the process how the gamification framework call the digital andon API is described in Section 2.2.4 of Deliverable D3.4 - Collaborative Platform for Work Process Support.

5.6.7 *Connection to Collaboration Platform*

Through Social Collaboration Platform the access to gamified processes is allowed and being enhanced, while platform offers access to gamified questions & answers tool and suggestion tool and simultaneously is gamified itself for increasing engagement. Additionally, the platform provides the users the possibility to participate in the posted games (operators & technicians) referring not only to inner-platform processes but also to real-life tasks and tasks arising from other gamified tools, such as AR applications. In addition, platform provides all of the gamification outcomes coming from all of the gamified processes, which the users can view, practice that is essential for motivating the users and enhance their interest of participate more.

5.6.7.1 *Gamification Support in the Collaboration Platform*

The supervisor can be informed about the participants' actions through the Social Collaboration Platform, as can any other user (operators & technicians). They have access to the gamification outcomes of the others, while every user has a personal section showing the personal awards, either coming from the individual or from team games (points, achievements, levels, badges), as well as the current participations in games and progress. Additionally, they can be informed for important gamification news through notifications.

The Social Collaboration Platform is the only way for the operators & technicians to be informed about the available games that have been published. Concerning the available games, they can be informed about the tasks included, the awards available to win, as well as the level of priority that the games have and every other game feature that the supervisor published with the game. In the personal section, users can view their progress, achievements, points, levels, badges and the games that they are currently participating in and have participated in, accompanied with their features such as the awards given and their leaderboards. Users are able to view the leaderboards for every game and additionally a leaderboard in the personal section where the overall ranking is presented. They can be notified for important updates as well.

Gamification provides the administrator of the platform with an admin user interface, which offers the ability to create gamified processes. In other words, the administrator can decide which actions

are going to be supported by gamified elements and what these elements are going to be. This interface is a completely customizable environment where the admin manages the whole game's behavior by setting rules and awards of four types. The awards can be scalar, sets, tangible objects and levels and they can be viewed on leaderboards that concern either individuals or teams.

The administrator starts by deciding which process to gamify, writes a name and a description for it and chooses if it is going to address individuals or teams. After defining the kind of game (individual or team game), if it is for individuals, the category needs to be defined. There is also the choice of "Everyone" so that every user of the platform can participate.

In the same tab, there is the ability to create a team and invite people to join it.

After having created a game, the administrator can attach actions and/or quests to this game. An action is a complete activity of a simple job which, when fulfilled, is considered as done. The action is a step of a whole process, which can be a daily job in a workplace. Many actions can consist of a mission in a custom game. Besides, quests are actions which can be fulfilled only within a time interval. Meaning that a quest can appear in a moment of activation and disappear after the ending date. Usually these activities are presented in notifications, informing the user of their availability. The administrator creates a quest by choosing one of the available actions, created before, and gives a new fancy name with an informative description of the scope of the quest as well as the award that is going to be gained. If the action does not exist, the administrator has to go to the actions section in order to create it and afterwards return to quests and create one. In the create frame, the administrator also sets the starting and ending day for this quest.

Moving on with the creation of the game, the administrator has to define the awards. As mentioned before, the awards can be of four types:

- scalars which are usually points, coins or something that follows this logic
- sets, which are groups of cups or medals or anything in this form
- tangible objects, which are sets of awards applied to real life, like coupons, day-off and more
- levels, which distinguish levels of experience usually

The administrator can combine all these elements by using the rule engine found in the Rules section. Rules are the basis of the gamification process because they define the whole behavior that a user must follow in order to achieve the award. There are three kinds of awards that describe the following behaviors:

- Rule for triggering an action N times
It means that the administrator can set how many times an action should be fulfilled in order to gain an award. The administrator chooses the award as well and additionally he/she can define if the rule is to be applied to a specific category of users or to everyone.
- Rule for gaining extra awards after having collected an amount of them
It means that the administrator can define that a user can achieve a more valuable award after having gained some others. For example, this applies usually to set of awards by setting that one can gain a silver medal if she already has 50 points.
- Rule for leveling up
It means that the administrator can arrange when a user is changing level by setting a threshold from one level to the next. This usually happens by setting a starting point for every level, which can be determined with points. Otherwise, the administrator can say that a level changes if a user has a specific amount of another award and she is already carrying the previous level title.

Moreover, there is a leaderboard in every gamified process which informs the administrator of the performance of the users, which may be very informative if combined with the actual processes. Finally, a choice with all the participants in the game is available, even if they have not collected any award yet in order to know which action users find interesting and which not.

Every user can see the available games in her profile tab, in achievements, and join or leave a game according to her preference. Each game provides a leader board for the user too, in order to be easier to decide whether to participate or not.

Every award, either scalar or set or level, is shown in the profile's tab too, to every user separately and personally while every user can see her connections' achievements too.

The gamification platform can connect with every tool that can gamify its actions by calling the web services that are implemented for this scope. It provides a multilingual interface for the end users by providing the ability of adding a new language when creating the game. Thus, the administrator of the platform is offered English as default and can add any other language in the dictionary along with the context. Furthermore, gamification keeps track of all actions triggered from every user and every game that has been created along with the awards that are gained in order to provide an informative data analytical tool. At last, the gamification platform and the social collaboration platform send messages and notifications to Digital Andon, informing users of the most important events happening real time.

5.6.8 **Dashboard**

An executive Dashboard for the administrator offers access to every Satisfactory project's component. The supported components are AIMMS, Gamification platform, Event Visualization, Analytics and User management. The dashboard provides a general view of KPIs relevant to important subjects of the Satisfactory project, provided by the aforementioned tools. It allows the monitoring of productivity in workplaces, of evaluation of the processes and provides a general abstract overview of performance of daily jobs. By offering data analytics from the implemented tools, the administrator can have a visual presentation of performance where she can identify any positive or negative trend. Moreover, as efficiency can be measured better, there is the ability to take better decisions based on collected business intelligence. On the other hand, it saves a lot of time because it provides instant knowledge instead of getting the same knowledge by running multiple reports. When setting dashboard analytics correctly, the administrator can identify quickly any outlier or correlation based on tracked history behavior. An additional purpose of the dashboard is to provide a way to easily read information by integrating multiple components to this unified interface.

The information on the dashboard is presented with charts, histograms and pie charts, set by default from the manufacturer of the dashboard, but there is also the ability for users to customize look and interaction. Colors are of great importance in the dashboard as they are very descriptive so they are used to articulate these elements more. The data that are displayed are real time so that they are useful and can help in correcting current problems that may arise as well as history data so that there could be comparisons for evaluating performance. The project's tools show the following information:

- **AIMMS**
 - ✓ The amount of tasks that exist
 - ✓ The amount of delayed tasks that should have started
 - ✓ The percentage of malfunctions to precautions
 - ✓ The amount of new tasks
- **Collaboration Platform**

- ✓ The amount of Q&As in per week
- ✓ The amount of posts per day
- **Gamification Platform**
 - ✓ Points gained from an action by a player
 - ✓ Badges gained from an action by a player
 - ✓ Most popular action fulfilled
 - ✓ Leaderboard for every game
- **Event Visualization**
 - ✓ Depth cameras events
 - ✓ Thermal cameras events
- **Analytics**
- **User Management**

The dashboard shows information which can be customized according to the end user but in general it pulls out the information without having to log into multiple systems. The dashboard is a web based interface so that anyone could access it from every browser.

5.6.9 ***Maintenance Game and the Social Collaboration Platform***

The Social Collaboration Platform of the SatisFactory Project is an element of the project designed and developed to achieve and increase worker satisfaction in the factory shop floors. There are many different aspects of social media embedded in the social collaboration platform. Live comments, fora, questions and answers are some of the aspects of the social collaboration platform.

Games on the platform are one of the newest and challenging ideas that can lead in worker satisfaction, especially when the games are designed to incorporate parts of the workers' daily activities. Playing a game while working leads to new interest for the performed task. It can also lead to attraction of the working environment for new and younger persons, which is one of the main objectives of the SatisFactory project.

The developed games on the platform are distributed amongst the different components of the project. Games about the augmented reality glasses and the gesture recognition are among them. Also, games about maintenance on a shop floor are developed and embedded in the social collaboration platform.

5.6.9.1 ***Maintenance Games***

The maintenance games were developed in order to improve the maintenance operations on the shop floor and include workers, in more active ways, during the procedures. Four games were developed for the maintenance part:

- AIMMS All Actors
- AIMMS Process Technicians
- AIMMS IT Technicians
- AIMMS Process Operators

Only certified users of the collaboration platform can join the games and gain points in the process. AIMMS users without an account on the collaboration platform cannot participate in the games

Figure 28: Join a Maintenance Game at the Social Collaboration Platform

Gradually, the connected users can join many different games on the platform. According to their position in the work schedule and the hierarchy of the shop floor, a worker is able to join different games and participate in all of them. Also, there is the possibility for a worker to leave the game, if it is necessary (for example when a worker needs to move to another position on the shop floor, where the maintenance games are not applicable, or when the worker quits his job). Although the worker may leave, his points, gathered at different games, remain in the platform. These are calculated in the grand total of the teams he participates in, and if he decides to return in the games in the future, he can continue with his already won points.

Figure 29: Leave the Game Options

5.6.9.2 *Participation in the Game – Instructions*

The Maintenance Games that have been developed are connected with the work scheduling and the tasks created by the iDSS in the Satisfactory project. For any of the games to be meaningful, there is a connection to maintenance tasks and the procedures followed the initiation of a maintenance task.

The first level of connection are the registered users. Any user of the iDSS task schedule can create a task, but only the users that are registered both at the iDSS and the social collaboration platform can participate in the games. If this requirement is fulfilled, a worker can create a task in the iDSS – AIMMS application. The new task can be seen by the iDSS and contains all necessary information about it: the kind of task, the user who created it, the broken asset, department criticality, etc.

The new task must be initiated. iDSS is able to understand which user is responsible for this task and what points it should delegate to them, because different actions lead to different points. It is also able to communicate the points to the social collaboration platform. When the social collaboration platform receives the task information from the iDSS, through the middleware, it has all the necessary fields to delegate the suitable points to the person that started the task. The points of each task are automatically delegated to the correct persons.


```

C:\Atlantis\idss>idss -- gamification
Total tasks:1386-last task 131017-last completed 131017
^C
C:\Atlantis\idss>idss -- gamification
'--gamification' is not recognized as an internal or external command,
operable program or batch file.

C:\Atlantis\idss>idss -- gamification
2017-02-03 14:32:11.718 [1] DEBUG ABE.IDSS.Program [(null)] - starting
Last task :131017
^C
C:\Atlantis\idss>idss -- gamification
2017-02-03 14:51:54.845 [1] DEBUG ABE.IDSS.Program [(null)] - starting
Last task :131017
Total tasks:1386-last task 131017-last completed 131017
Total tasks:1386-last task 131017-last completed 131017
New Task 131026 0 3 ISAD - Daily check actions 25040
send start action <15> for game AIMMS
<\"result\":'OK\"'>
Total tasks:1387-last task 131026-last completed 131017
  
```

Figure 30: The console application of the Gamification Component of iDSS

A view of the iDSS console application. In this view, the new task can be seen together with the workers who created it. From this moment, the iDSS application is able to recognize the worker responsible for the task, it can notify the social collaboration platform and delegate the corresponding points to the workers. Points are delegated for starting, completing and commenting on a certain task. Each of the above actions provides a different number of points to the workers and their teams. Starting a task is awarded by five points, commenting on a task is awarded with ten and completing a task is awarded with fifteen points.

Figure 31: Points delegated for starting a task

The points from starting a new task have been delegated. A new task gains five points. These points are assigned to all actors, because when the task was created, the responsible workers were different from the worker groups that participate in the game. If the worker was an IT Technician the points would be given both to “All Actors” and “IT Technicians” as it is highlighted with yellow.

As it is shown, the points gained are appointed to two different teams. The reason for this is that the team “All Actors” is a more general team and contains all the other teams existing in the Maintenance game. “All Actors” gain the points of all the participating workers and teams. Their points are the grand total of the points everyone have gained participating in the maintenance game.

6 DIGITAL ANDON

The Digital Andon is a SatisFactory component that represents a Novel HMI and is meant to be deployed at the shop floor level. It acts as a content management system and allows multilayer data visualization. This component adds the advance functionality of display dynamic information, creating multiple layers. Each layer is provided with its own regions and resources in order to increase the dynamic nature of the component itself, allowing third-party in-factory components to draw on every SatisFactory enabled display in a more comprehensive manner, by addressing directly the desired resource through the exposed API.

Figure 32, on the left side, shows a schema with three overlay layers. The leftmost one is a background layer and does not contain any regions. Two regions that respectively contain a shape and an image resource compose the second overlay. The third layer contains a single region with a text resource. On the right is shown the resulting image produced by the andon.

Figure 32: Multi-layer overlay template

The Andon API (cf. Section 6.1.1) allows defining and managing overlays, regions and resources that are visualized using andon templates.

6.1 COMPONENT VIEW

Figure 33 shows the component view of the digital andon. Clients can use the design component API to create overlays, regions and to assign the correspondent resources. During these operations, the visualization devices continue to display unchanged information from the release component.

When a screen design is completed, a client can flush its information to the release component to refresh the correspondent visualization device. Visualization device, if not restarted, continue to display the last information received also if the server is unreachable.

Figure 33: Andon component view

All andon functionalities of both design and release components are accessible using a REST API. The fundamental API concept is the resource. A resource is an object with a type, associated data, relationships to other resources identified by a specific Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs). Client and server exchange textual representations of these resources using HTTP standard methods (GET, POST, PUT, PATCH and DELETE). Andon APIs uses a JSON data model for resource representations.

Resources can be grouped into collections. Each collection can contain only one type of resource. Resources are logically designed to be children of other resources and therefore are called nested resources.

6.1.1 **API resource and visual representation**

The Andon API root resource is called *screen*. Figure 34 shows the visual representation of a generic screen. It includes a top area that contains logo and title and a bottom area for generic contents.

Figure 34: Visual screen representation

The screen resource format is described in the table below.

Table 26: Properties of the screen resource

Property	Description	Format	Mandatory
id	Unique identifier for the resource. The server normally generates the identifier at resource creation time.	Number	No
titleHeight	Height of the title. Default value is 64px.	'px', '%' or 'vh'. Units description is available here .	No
titleFont	Font of the title. Default value is 'sans-serif'	Available fonts are described here .	No
titleFontSize	Title font size. Default value is 35px.	Same as titleHeight	No
titleText	Title text. Default is 'Satisfactory - Digital Andon'	String	No
titleColor	Title color. Default value is '#000000'	Hex RGB color(e.g. '#ff0000') or rgb(a) color (e.g. 'rgba (255,0,0,0.8)')	No

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Property	Description	Format	Mandatory
titleBackColor	Title background color. Default value is '#ff7f00'	Same as titleColor	No
titleHAlign	Title text horizontal alignment. Default is 'left'	'left','right' or 'center'	No
titleVisible	Specify if the title is visible. Default is 'true'	'true' or 'false'	No
contentBackColor	Content area background color. Default value is '#ffffff'	Same as titleColor	No
description	Description of the screen. Default is null	String	No
lastRefresh	Is the time of last modification of the screen resource. This is a read-only value and cannot be modified by client	Date and time	No

Each screen content can contain three different nested resource called *shape*, *text* and *image*. Their properties are indicated in Table 27, Table 28 and Table 29.

Table 27: Properties of the image resource

Property	Description	Format	Mandatory
id	Unique identifier for the resource. The server normally generates the identifier at resource creation time.	Number	No
x	X position of the resource in screen content	It can be an absolute (e.g. '20px') or relative length respect to the screen content width (e.g. '20%')	Yes
y	Y position of the resource in screen content	It can be an absolute (e.g. '20px') or relative length respect to the screen content height (e.g. '20%')	Yes
z	Depth of the resource	Number	No
data	Base64 encoded image	String	Yes
width	Width of the image on screen. If not present the image width is used	Same as x	No
height	Height of image on screen. If not	Same as y	No

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	present the image height is used		
format	Describe the image type. Default is 'image/png'.	'image/png' or 'image/jpeg'	No
description	Description of the image. Default is null	String	No
preserveAspectRatio	If true the application will respect the image aspect ratio	'true' or 'false'	No

Figure 35 shows on the left side the image area with preserveAspectRatio set to true. On the right side the preserveAspectRatio is set to false and the image is stretched to fill all the defined region.

Figure 35: Visual image representation

Table 28: Properties of the shape resource

Property	Description	Format	Mandatory
id	Unique identifier for the resource. The server normally generates the identifier at resource creation time.	Number	No
x	X position of the resource in screen content	It can be an absolute (e.g. '20px') or relative length respect to the screen content width (e.g. '20%')	Yes
y	Y position of the resource in screen content	It can be an absolute (e.g. '20px') or relative length respect to the screen content height (e.g. '20%')	Yes
z	Depth of the resource	Number	No

Property	Description	Format	Mandatory
type	Shape type	'rectangle' or 'ellipse'	Yes
width	Width of the shape on screen	Same as x	Yes
height	Height of the shape on screen	Same as y	Yes
color	Shape color. Default value is '#000000'	Hex RGB color(e.g. '#ff0000') or rgb(a) color (e.g. 'rgba(255,0,0,0.8)')	No
description	Description of the shape. Default is null	String	No
fill	If true the shape is filled with color	'true' or 'false'	No

Figure 36 shows on the left side a rectangular shape and on the left an elliptic one.

Figure 36: Visual shape representation

Table 29: Properties of the text resource

Property	Description	Format	Mandatory
id	Unique identifier for the resource. The server normally generates the identifier at resource creation time.	Number	No
id	Unique identifier for the resource.	Number	No

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Property	Description	Format	Mandatory
	The server normally generates the identifier at resource creation time.		
x	X position of the resource in screen content	It can be an absolute (e.g. '20px') or relative position respect to the screen content width (e.g. '20%')	Yes
y	Y position of the resource in screen content	It can be an absolute (e.g. '20px') or relative position respect to the screen content height (e.g. '20%')	Yes
z	Depth of the resource	Number	No
width	Width of text rectangle	Same as x	No
height	Height of text rectangle	Same as y	No
hAlign	Text horizontal alignment. Non used if width or height are not present	'left', 'right' or 'center'	No
vAlign	Text vertical alignment. Non used if width or height are not present	'top', 'bottom' or 'middle'	No
text	Resource text	String	Yes
font	Text font. Default value is 'sans-serif'	Available fonts are described here .	No
fontSize	Text font size. Default value is 5%.	It can be an absolute (e.g. '20px') or relative length respect to the screen content height (e.g. '20%')	No
description	Description of the text. Default is null	String	No
color	Text color. Default value is '#000000'	Hex RGB color(e.g. '#ff0000') or rgb(a) color (e.g. 'rgba(255,0,0,0.8)')	No

The text resource can have two visual representations (Figure 37):

The text will be always displayed on a single line; special characters (e.g. carriage return '\n') are displayed as normal text.

The following figure shows the two possible operating modes concerning text representation:

- the absolute positioning (left): only x and y of the bottom left point of the text region are required. The text is displayed using the font information provided;
- relative positioning inside a rectangle (right): this mode requires also width and height of the selected rectangle. The text is displayed inside the rectangle using provided alignment information.

Figure 37: Visual text representation

Figure 38 shows middle, top and bottom vertical alignments on top line and center, left and right horizontal alignments on bottom line.

Figure 38: Text alignment

If text overflows the assigned region in relative positioning the outer parts of the text are not displayed as shown in Figure 39.

Figure 39: Text overflow

6.1.2 *Design component*

This chapter reports the methods that must be used to define and modify the previously defined resources. For the sake of simplicity, all examples has been done using the curl command, but any

other REST client library can be used with the same methods. For the same reason, all URI refers to 127.0.0.1 IP address and port 3010.

All API requests returns always a proper HTTP code. In the following, an example of successful response is provided:

```
< HTTP/1.1 200 OK
< X-Powered-By: Express
< Content-Type: application/json; charset=utf-8
< Content-Length: 2205
< Date: Wed, 13 Jul 2016 13:33:26 GMT
< ...
```

Table 30 HTTP codes returned from the Digital Andon API

Code	Description
200 OK	Response to a successful GET, PUT, PATCH or DELETE
201 Created	Response to a successful POST. Contains a Location header pointing to the location of the new resource
400 Bad Request	The request is malformed, such as if the body does not parse
403 Forbidden	When user doesn't have access to the resource
404 Not Found	When a non-existent resource is requested
415 Unsupported Media Type	If incorrect content type or accept header was provided as part of the request
500 Internal Server Error	If an unexpected error occurred on the server

In addition to the proper HTTP code, also a JSON message with request results is sent. Examples follow:

```
{"result":"success"}
{"result":"success","id":"/api/design/screens/3"}
{"result":"error","msg":"Malformed input: Unexpected property param"}
```

Every visualization device must be assigned to a screen resource. Screen resource collection URI is **http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/**

Two HTTP methods are available on screen collection:

- POST: add a new screen to the collection. To create a new screen the CURL command can be used.
- **curl -H "Content-type: application/json" -X POST http://ip:port/api/design/ screens/ -d '{"titleVisible":false}'**

-
- can be used to create a new screen with all default properties but without title bar. If successful a 201 Created response is returned by the server and the location header is filled with the id of the created resource (e.g. Location: /api/design/screens/0);
- GET: return all the available screens in a JSON array. Two Boolean parameters are available for the request: nested and sorted. If the first parameter is enabled also the nested resources (shapes, images and texts) are returned. If also sorted is enabled nested resources are sorted by depth.
-
- **curl -H "Content-type: application/json" -X GET http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/**
-
- returns the following JSON array:

```
{
  "id": "0",
  "titleHeight": "64px",
  "titleFont": "sans-serif",
  "titleText": "Satisfactory - Digital Andon",
  "titleFontSize": "35px",
  "titleColor": "#000000",
  "titleBackColor": "#FF7F00",
  "titleVisible": "true",
  "titleHAlign": "left",
  "contentBackColor": "#ffffff",
  "description": "",
  "lastRefresh": "2016-07-13T14:03:17.892Z",
  {...}
}
```

An example of request for nested resources follows:

```
curl -X GET http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens?nested=true&sorted=true
```

A specific screen is reachable using the URI **http:// 127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/screenId**
The screenId is the identifier of the screen (e.g. **http:// 127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/0**).

The following operations are available:

- GET: similar to the GET request on screens collection but doesn't return an array but only the screen identified by the screenId. In addition to previous parameters, the method also offers

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a third parameter called time. If time is present, the server answers to the request only when the screen lastRefresh is greater than time. The following is a request example:

-
- **curl -X GET**
http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/0?nested=true&sorted=true&time=2016-07-14T09:15:24.909Z
-
- DELETE: delete the screen identified by the screenId. The curl request is:
-
- **curl -X DELETE** http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/0
-
- PUT: update the screen identified by screenId. All optional undefined properties of the request are set to their default values. If before PUT the screen has the following information

```
...  
  "titleText": "Test",  
  "titleFontSize": "35px",  
  "titleColor": "#000000",  
  "titleBackColor": "#FF7F00",  
  "titleVisible": "true",  
  ...
```

After the following request

```
curl -H "Content-type: application/json" -X PUT  
http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/2 -d '{"titleVisible":false}'
```

The resource status is:

```
...  
  "titleText": "Satisfactory - Digital Andon",  
  "titleFontSize": "35px",  
  "titleColor": "#000000",  
  "titleBackColor": "#FF7F00",  
  "titleVisible": "false",  
  ...
```

The titleVisible property has become false as required but also the titleText was set to the default value.

- PATCH: partially update the screen identified by screenId. All optional undefined properties of the request are left unchanged. After the following PATCH request

-
- **curl -H "Content-type: application/json" -X PUT**
http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/2 -d '{"titleVisible":false}'
-
- The screen resource status is:

```
...  
"titleText":"Test",  
"titleFontSize":"35px",  
"titleColor":"#000000",  
"titleBackColor":"#FF7F00",  
"titleVisible":"false",  
...
```

Only the required property `titleVisible` is changed with the requested value.

The nested resources collections are accessible using the following URI:

- **http://ip:port/api/design/screens/screenId/texts**
- **http://ip:port/api/design/screens/screenId/images**
- **http://ip:port/api/design/screens/screenId/shapes**

These collections have the same GET and POST methods as the screen collection. For example to add a text to the screen 0 the following command can be used:

```
curl -H "Content-type: application/json" -X POST http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/0/texts  
-d '{"x":"35%", "y":"20%", "z":"2", "text":"Text"}'
```

and to get all texts:

```
curl -X GET http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/0/texts.
```

These collections can be sorted by depth with `sorted` parameter.

Clients can also operate on the single resources using GET, DELETE, PUT and PATCH method as described for screen resource. For example to delete the image 0 resource from screen 0 the following command can be used:

```
curl -X DELETE http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/0/images/0
```

Images must be loaded using base64 encoding. A convenient method that can be used on Linux-based OS to perform the required base64 encoding is:

```
echo '{"x":"10%","y":"10%","data":"" > image.txt
cat logo.png | base64 >> image.txt
echo ""}' >> image.txt
curl -H "Content-type: application/json" -X POST
http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/0/images -d @image.txt
```

When all design operations are completed the design information can be flushed to the release mode. In order to perform this operation, the following command must be used:

```
curl -H "Content-type: application/json" -X PATCH
http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/0/flush
```

It is also possible to select an animation used by the server for screen refresh:

```
curl -H "Content-type: application/json" -X PATCH -d '{"entryAnimation":"slide-from-top-
animation", "exitAnimation":"slide-down-animation"}'
http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/design/screens/0/flush
```

Using this animation, for example, the old screen slides from the bottom edge of the view (exitAnimation) and the new one enters from top edge (enterAnimation). The title bar, if present, is not affected by the animation.

Figure 40: Refresh animation

Following animations are available:

- fade-in-animation and fade-out-animation;
- scale-up-animation and scale-down-animation;
- slide-up-animation and slide-down-animation;
- slide-from-top-animation and slide-from-bottom-animation;
- slide-left-animation and slide-right-animation;
- slide-from-left-animation and slide-from-right-animation.

6.1.3 *Release component*

The release component has the same resources as the design component but cannot be modified. For this reason only GET methods are available.

The URI that must be used are the same of the design component without the design

curl -X GET http://127.0.0.1:3010/api/screens

All modifications must be made in design mode and then flushed to the release component. Normally these API are only used by the visualization device as described in the next chapter..

6.2 *DATA VISUALIZATION*

Visualization devices that want to display the release component data can use the default template made available by the digital andon server. The default template can be displayed using browser with the URI **http://127.0.0.1:3010/view?id=screenId**. The screenId is the identifier of the screen resource that must be visualized.

Figure 41 shows the searching view of the template that remains visible until the first flush of the screen resource with id 0.

Figure 41: Template searching view

After each flush, the visualization area is refreshed using release component information and eventually using the requested animations. Figure 42 show a visualization example obtained with the attached script test.sh.

Figure 42: Screen visualization without title

To allow clients to view all modifications made to design components directly when they occur, without waiting for a flush command to be triggered, a design page is available at the following URL: <http://127.0.0.1:3010/view?id=screenId&design=true>

6.3 PUBLIC DISPLAY MESSAGE BOARD

This module acts as a bridge between the LinkSmart MQTT broker and the Digital Andon component, providing a centralized message board that displays opportunely formatted events, received from designated MQTT topics.

Figure 43 Component View

The message board provides a customizable template, composed by a title and a vertical list of text fields displayed on the screen through the Digital Andon API. Figure 44 shows a generic template with four text fields.

Figure 44: Digital Andon message board template

New events received from MQTT are parsed and displayed on the upper text field. All previously received messages are slid down from the bottom edge of the view using a transition effect.

The whole process requires a one-time setup to define template layout, MQTT topics, message format and parsing rules. The configuration file is a JSON file composed by three sections:

```
{
  "andon" : { ... },
  "ui" : { ... },
  "mqtt" : { ... }
}
```

Each section is detailed in the following sections.

6.3.1 **Andon configuration section**

The *andon* section contains both the URL to enable remote access to the Digital Andon API and the identifier of the Digital Andon screen:

```
"andon" : {
  "url": "http://127.0.0.1:3010",
  "screen": "2"
}
```


6.3.2 MQTT configuration section

This section contains the information required to receive and parse MQTT messages. The configuration format is the following:

```
"mqtt" : {
    "url":"http://127.0.0.1:1883",
    "topics": [ ... ],
    "clearTopic": { "topic":"Satisfactory/Andon/Clear", "qos":1 }
}
```

The MQTT broker URL for remote subscription is provided by the *URL* field. On the other hand, the *clearTopic* field defines the topic that can be used to reset all message boxes to the default text, as provided in the *UI* section (see chapter 6.3.3).

Topics field is the array of topics to which the connector will subscribe. A generic topic is described below:

```
{"topic":"Satisfactory/Andon/Info", "qos":1, "type":"text", "level":"info"}
```

The first two fields, *topic* and *qos*, identify respectively the MQTT topic name and quality of service for broker subscription. The *type* field defines the format of the messages received from the topic and can range from simple text to JSON and XML. The last field, namely *level*, identifies the message level and the corresponding icon type. Three levels and icons are available: *info*, *warn* or *alert* (see Figure 44).

With text *type*, any messages received from the topic are automatically injected, without modifications, into the templates for triggering a display update. To display a more complex message structure, two special parsing commands can be provided inside the square brackets:

- The \$ command to search a specific text inside the MQTT message
- The # command to get a specific part of the MQTT topic

The following example shows the usage of the command inside the *message* field for a generic fall event from the Gesture and Content Recognition Manager (GCRM):

```
{
"topic":"Satisfactory/GCRM/+/Fall Detection",
"qos":1,
"type":"xml",
"message":"Fall event from [$CIDEM.ShopFloor.SFEvents.EventList.Event. SourceID] on station [#2]",
"level":"alert"
}
```

With this configuration the connector subscribes itself on all the MQTT topics Satisfactory/GCRM/+/FallDetection where the wildcard character + can be any kind of station identifier (typically a number).

For example, a GCRM that is installed on the smart assembly station 22 would normally send events on topic Satisfactory/GCRM/22/ FallDetection with the following CIDEM XML format:

<CIDEM>

```

<ShopFloor>
  <ShopFloorID>SHOPFLOOR_ISMB</ShopFloorID>
  <SFEvents>
    <EventList>
      <Event>
        <ID>GCRM_752acb9c-970e-41d6-9c4e-l23ks</ID>
        <Type>Fall</Type>
        <TimeStamp>2017-03-01T11:16:36.197</TimeStamp>
        <SourceID>GCRM</SourceID>
        <Content>
          <Alert>
            <ID>GCRM_752acb9c-970e-41d6-9c4e-l23ks</ID>
            <Description>Fall</Description>
          </Alert>
        </Content>
      </Event>
    </EventList>
  </SFEvents>
</ShopFloor>
</CIDEM>

```

When the connector receives the event it searches for [\${CIDEM.ShopFloor.SFEvents.EventList.Event.SourceID}] XML tag obtaining the text highlighted in yellow in the example above. The second parsing command [#2] is instead replaced with the correspondent part of the topic (e.g. Satisfactory/GCRM/22/FallDetection). The result is displayed in Figure 45 .

Figure 45: Parsing result

6.3.3 *UI configuration section*

This section contains the message board and the template layout:

```

"ui" : {
  "screen": {
    "titleVisible": "true",
    "titleText": "Notification panel",
    "titleHAlign": "center",
    "titleHeight": "128px",

```

```

        "titleFontSize":"64px",
        "contentBackColor":"#d9dde2"
    },
    "flush": {
        "entryAnimation":"slide-from-top-animation",
        "exitAnimation":"slide-down-animation"
    },
    "shape": {
        "color":"#f7f8f9"
    },
    "text": {
        "hAlign":"left",
        "fontSize":"8%"
    },
    "vSeparator":"3",
    "hSeparator":"5",
    "imgWidth":"15",
    "rows":"4",
    "defaultText":"Not available"
}

```

The screen sub-section contains the screen resource configuration. The shape and text sub-section defines respectively the format of both shape and text the of the message box. The flush sub-section contains the transition effect shown when a new message is received from MQTT and flushed on the display.

The rows field defines the total number of text fields displayed by the message board. The hSeparator and vSeparator represent respectively the distance between two consecutive rows and the margin from the screen border as described in the figure below:

Figure 46 Message board configuration parameters

The *defaultText* is the text displayed by the message board when an event is received on the clearTopic.

STARTING THE SERVER

The server requires a *node.js* environment.

Before starting the server, it is necessary to install all the dependencies (network is required). An installation script that works on Linux-based OS systems, called **prepare.sh** must be used.

The server can be launched with **node server.js** command. The server starts on default **3010** port. The default port can be changed adding the port parameter: **PORT=8080 node server.js**

A test script is also provided and it displays the sample view shown in Figure 42. The script executes a set of sequential curl commands every 5 seconds. The design page can be used to watch the modification as soon as they happen.

6.4 *STARTING THE MESSAGE BOARD*

Exactly like the Digital Andon server, also the message board requires the *node.js* environment to be installed. A package.json file is provided with the application. It installs all dependencies with the npm tool (e.g. the CLI command **npm install**). In order to download the dependencies, a working network connection is required.

After the configuration process has taken place the message board can be started with the CLI command **node app.js**. The reset parameter (e.g. CLI command **node app.js reset**) must be issued to apply configuration modifications to the interface template.

6.5 *OPEN ISSUES AND TROUBLESHOOTING*

This chapter lists some issues or still missing functions on the current release:

- The API doesn't provide an authentication method;
- The server has a very verbose log system. It would be better to attach log files to bug reports.

7 WIRELESS CONNECTION IN HOSTILE ENVIRONMENTS

The final chapter reports about robust wireless ICT infrastructure for hostile environments. This is a relevant deployment precondition for the concepts that are selected for implementation in this deliverable. All selected concepts will be implemented using a distributed architecture, i.e. there is a need for data communication between components. On the shop floor, the data communication will most likely have wireless parts because wired infrastructure is not available and deployable to many areas. But the shop floor also has special requirements to such a wireless infrastructure.

The wireless communication offers a wide range of advantages over the wired one, especially in the context of Internet of Things (IoT). For instance, in the industrial environments a large number of sensors gather data to help in smooth running of industrial processes. These sensors are also used for collecting environmental data, such as temperature and humidity. This data is used to guarantee the health and safety of workers at the shop floor, by warning the workers in real-time about a dangerous situation, when the sensors get abnormal data. In particular, in large scale deployments it is preferred wireless sensors instead of wired, because deploying and managing a large number of wired sensors at the shop floor can be a tricky task, in terms of cost and maintenance. However, reliability in wireless communication can be a challenging task, especially, in harsh environments. Since, the data acquired from sensors become critical for the correct operation of industrial processes and for the safety of workers at the shop floor, a robust and reliable wireless connection must be guaranteed. Keeping these requirements in mind, to provide robustness and reliability in communication, two infrastructures have been designed, namely single-radio and multi-radio infrastructures.

The Single-Radio (SR) infrastructure is based on a 6LoWPAN communication protocol and consists of a SR gateway (SRGW), Sensor Nodes (SNs) and a Spectrum Sensing Node (SSN). The robustness in the SR infrastructure is achieved by exploiting a frequency agility module, called Spectrum Manager (SM), inside SRGW. This module enables SNs to select the best channel, based on information gathered from SSN, for data transfer, in case high interference or data loss is detected on the current operating channel. In general, SSNs are capable of sensing the channel occupancies of the IEEE 802.15.4 frequency band, which shares the spectrum centered at 2.4GHz with IEEE 802.11 (Wi-Fi), and 802.15.1 (Bluetooth) wireless standards. Due to relatively lower power of the IEEE 802.15.4 radios, in addition to the industrial interferences, there is also a high probability of interference from the above mentioned radio technologies. The channel occupancy information gathered by SSN is sent to SM, which analyses if the current operating channel has occupancy higher than a predefined threshold for a certain amount of time. Then, the SM suggests to the SNs to switch to the best channel as observed by the SSNs. The SM, which typically runs on a SRGW node, also observes the packet loss information and packet delay. For instance, if the packet loss rate is below a specific threshold the channel switch operation is not performed. Moreover, the SR infrastructure monitors the connectivity of SNs and has self-healing capabilities, in case of loss of connection. The SRGW was developed using Raspberry Pi 2. The 6LoWPAN interface for SRGW is provided by Border Router (BR), which forwards information from SNs to SRGW and vice versa. Both SSN and BR are developed using Telos rev. B (Sky mote) platform[1]. The SN is developed on Zolertia Z1[2], which uses on board temperature sensor. The architecture is shown in figure below. More details about Single-radio node can be found in Deliverable D4.1.

Figure 47: Single-Radio Architecture

Multi-Radio (MR) infrastructure has been developed as well for the harsh environments to guarantee a higher degree of reliability not achievable by the SR infrastructure. MR infrastructure consists of a Multi-Radio Gateway (MRGW) and Multi-Radio Nodes (MRNs). Both MRGW and MRNs are designed to connect to each other using multiple interfaces, Wi-Fi and 6LoWPAN. MRGW also has a Spectrum Sensing Node (SSN) attached to it, to observe IEEE 802.15.4 channels for 6LoWPAN interface. The MRN provides Wi-Fi and 6LoWPAN connectivity to the sensor attached to it. In particular, a MRN observes at runtime communication parameters such as RSSI, packet loss, and packet delay of each available interface at regular intervals and it selects the most reliable interface among 6LoWPAN and Wi-Fi for data transfer. The MRN has on board a dedicated computing capability to make decision for choosing the most reliable interface, by using a cognitive algorithm. Concerning the 6LoWPAN interface, the MR logic leverages all the capabilities of the SR infrastructure presented above. In addition, MR infrastructure has network monitoring capabilities, which add self-healing feature, so, in case of broken communication link, it can reconfigure the whole network by itself. MRGW and MRNs are developed on Raspberry Pi 2. Telos rev. B (Sky mote) platform[1] is used to provide 6LoWPAN interface to both, MRGW and MRN. The architecture of MR infrastructure is shown in figure below. More details about MR infrastructure are given in Deliverable D4.1.

Figure 48: Multi-Radio Architecture

8 CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of the present deliverable is to document the iterative process of ideation and concept development in order to achieve the fundamental goal of increasing the attractiveness of the working environment for the workers. This deliverable described the concepts perceived using the user-centered and value-oriented design techniques based on the requirements gathered in WP1.

D2.3 explained the evolution of the concepts behind various platforms designed to encourage the social interaction between workers in factories. For example, the social interaction platform aims to improve the social aspect of the working experience for the workers. The gamification framework aims to introduce a sense of playfulness and competition to stimulate collaboration and motivate the workers to do their tasks in a better way. This deliverable also described how various components such as the platform for Suggestions for Improvement was gamified to contribute to the whole gamification environment created in the factory. It also explained how the digital andon system works and how can it be used as one visualization system for the gamification framework.

Conclusively, this deliverable documented the fundamental concepts perceived for the development of various use cases and the iterative approach how these concepts evolved. Details about the interface designs and the implementation details of the selected concepts are described in D3.2 - Situated and attractive information exchange techniques for workers and D3.4 - Collaborative platform for work process support, respectively.

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